

EXPLORATORY SEQUENTIAL STUDY ON PARENTAL ABSENCE AND MORAL DEVELOPMENT AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH OVERSEAS FILIPINO WORKER PARENTS

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Exploratory Sequential Study on Parental Absence and Moral Development among Senior High School Students with Overseas Filipino Worker Parents

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Abstract

This study examined the lived experience, level, and relationship of SHS High School Students with Overseas Filipino Worker Parents (OFW) in terms of their Parental Absence and Moral Development. Utilizing the Mixed method design specifically an exploratory sequential study the research was conducted in Private Higher Educational Institutions in Calamba City, Laguna among Senior High School Students aged 15-18 years old which used homogeneous purposive sampling and snowball sampling techniques. The data were analyzed using thematic analysis, descriptive statistics, and Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient. This study generated ten (10) superordinate themes. For parental absence, these were: Various Influences of Family Dynamics; Consistent and Open Communication; Emotional Cut-Off and Various Emotional Reactions; and Maintaining a Sense of Self Amidst Familial Challenges. Correspondingly, the themes that emerged from Moral Development were Handling Criticism and Emotional Reaction; Influence of Social Dynamics and External Factors on Decision-Making; Emotional Regulation and Coping Mechanisms; Adherence to Laws and Regulations; Respect and Obedience to Authority Figures; and Ethical Behavior and Accountability. Moreover, the study revealed that although the SHS students had parental absence they developed independence and self-reliance and had a high understanding of what is morally right and wrong. There were significant relationships between the Various Influences of Family Dynamics and Ethical Behavior and Accountability ($r=0.267$, $p < .05$), Consistent and Open Communication and Emotional Regulation and coping mechanism ($r=0.277$, $p < .05$), Emotional Cut-Off and Various Emotional Reactions and Social Dynamics on Decision-Making ($r=0.274$, $p < .05$). This study also proposed an action plan that was focused on life guidance, regulation on the expression of emotion, decision skill management, proper acceptance of emotions, and awareness of basic rules and regulations among the SHS students.

Keywords: *parental absence, moral development, exploratory sequential study*

Introduction

The basic family consists of parents and children. It is also the basic unit of society where values, culture, beliefs, and the fundamentals of a person are developed. Being inside and growing up in a complete family is important for the holistic growth of a person, especially for children. But things can change if parents do not live with their children due to so many reasons. Their absence can affect the overall development of their children.

For this reason, Annor et al. (2024) stated that parental absence has been widely defined as the temporary or permanent absence of one or both parents due to a variety of circumstances, including divorce, incarceration, evacuating, parental death (orphanhood), and migration. There were many reasons why parents or parents were absent in the life of their children, some were intentional, and some were not. But regardless of the reasons, it still can influence how their children develop.

Furthermore, one of the common reasons why parents are absent from the lives of their children is because they work. Work can consume a lot of time for the parents. They need to earn more because they have children and families to support. According to Gray (2024), people had a system in place where people worked for wages to distribute necessities, and those wages were still set at a level that required many people to work long hours to support their families.

Moreover, parents who were mostly absent in the lives of their children were working abroad or they are migrant workers. The most recent global estimate indicates that in 2020, around 281 million people were residing as international migrants, making up approximately 3.6 percent of the overall global population, according to International Organization for Migration, (2023). In the Philippines, this situation persisted for quite some time. The Philippines consistently ranked among the leading countries in terms of sending their citizens to work abroad. According to the United Nations Network on Migration, the demand for overseas Filipino workers (OFWs) is on the rise. In 2019, the Philippines had an estimated 5.4 million people living abroad, with approximately 2.3 million of them being OFWs.

Additionally, Cherry (2022) defined moral development as the process by which individuals learned to distinguish between right and wrong (morality) and used moral reasoning to reason between the two. Morality was important because it guided people to do what was right and prevented them from doing wrong. It should be developed, especially during childhood and teenage years. This can be their anchor in living a good life, steering them away from the dangers of wrong decisions.

Similarly, according to OASH (2021), adolescents' moral development during this stage of life promoted both their best health and social engagement. For instance, studies connected spirituality and involvement in religion to better social relationships, increased self-

worth, and decreased rates of substance abuse. Adolescents frequently wanted to talk to their parents and other adults to be their guide. The adults around them especially their parents were the essential key for the child or the adolescents to develop their moral abilities and have a healthier view of life. If morality was not developed during this time, the person would struggle and find it hard to cope, get along, and blend in on his or her environment.

In the Philippine context, according to Gozum and Sarmiento (2021), Filipino families were renowned for being child centered. Parents made numerous sacrifices and made wise investments for their kids' benefit. They had the highest influence on a child's holistic development, especially morality. But to be able to provide for their children, some chose to be away and work overseas. This could help in terms of finances but affect the overall growth of the child because they looked for a role model that can guide them and without this guidance, they were more challenged in choosing the right and avoiding the wrong thing.

Furthermore, according to Dominguez and Hall (2022), the discrepancy between a child's moral development and their behavior in different situations was primarily due to their parents' failure to fulfill their role in upbringing. Family disintegration happens during a child's crucial developmental stage when they experience separation from one or both parents due to labor migration. These circumstances negatively affected how the child grew and developed, influencing their physical, emotional, mental, and moral growth. This added a burden on how they decided what was right or wrong. There were also long-term effects of this, which could arise during adulthood.

Likewise, according to Jandial (2023), the environment in which a child grows up influences their attitude on doing what is right and wrong. The relationship between parents and children plays a vital role in molding a child's personality and morality. This supported the notion that, during a child's critical developmental years, family disintegration could occur when they experienced separation from their parents because of labor migration. This situation affected both the environment in which they were raised and their physical emotional, psychological, and moral growth. Ensuring that healthy children can develop their cognitive potential to the fullest, stable, and secure environments are imperative during and after childhood (Dominguez & Hall, 2022).

A study conducted by Dewangan (2021) mentioned that there was a strong relationship between behavioral deviance and the absence of parents among adolescents. As per the research, 96% of the respondents reported that school students engaged in deviant behaviors, such as defying authority figures, theft, truancy, drug abuse, and so on because of having an absentee parent. This means that the adolescents were finding it hard whenever they were away from their parents, their holistic development was also affected because of this.

Considering this, the study was conducted to determine the relationship between the level of perceived parental absence and the level of moral development of Senior High School Students with OFW Parents. The researcher would also be undertaking another approach in this study which was an exploratory sequential method of mixed-method research that would also contribute to existing knowledge on how this approach would commonly utilize in this field. With the provided situation, the researcher deemed the study highly pertinent and believed that this needed acknowledgment in the present generation. This can be applied not only to children with parents overseas and parents yearning for their children's presence but also to aid society in gaining a deeper understanding of its underlying truths. Furthermore, the researcher who was currently working as an OSAS coordinator was concerned with the present study since adolescents nowadays show adverse defiance of their moral upbringing and minimal attention and appreciation about their relationship with their parents who tirelessly work abroad to give them the comfortable life they deserve.

Research Objectives

The main direction of this study was to determine the lived experience and identify the level of the senior high school students in terms of their parental absence and character development, as well as to determine if there was a significant relationship between parental absence and moral development. Specifically, the study aimed to accomplish the following objectives:

1. Determine the lived experience of senior high school students based on their parental absence and moral development.
2. Identify the parental absence level among Senior High School students.
3. Identify the moral development level among Senior High School students.
4. Determine if there is a significant relationship between parental absence and moral development levels among Senior High School students.
5. Propose an action plan.

Methodology

Research Design

According to Creswell and Creswell (2023), mixed methods involve the deliberate integration of strong quantitative and qualitative research techniques to weigh the respective advantages of each. This approach enabled researchers to employ a variety of methods, merging inductive and deductive reasoning, and overcoming the constraints associated with relying solely on quantitative or qualitative research.

Furthermore, the research utilized Exploratory Sequential Design. According to Dawadi et al. (2021), this model involved a three-part

investigation where a researcher initially operated based on the constructivist principle. In the initial phase, the researcher delves deeply into a particular issue. As they progressed to the second phase, they transitioned to the post-positivist principle to pinpoint variables and assess statistical trends. In this approach, qualitative data was initially collected and analyzed, followed by the subsequent collection, and testing of quantitative data. This methodology initiated the gathering and examination of qualitative data. Drawing upon the qualitative insights, quantitative measures or instruments were formulated, and subsequently, the researcher quantitatively examined the identified variable. The interpretation involved understanding how the quantitative data generalizes and extends the qualitative findings.

Additionally, regarding the incorporation of this framework, integration commenced with the creation of a quantitative measure derived from qualitative outcomes. Also, integration occurs after the completion of the quantitative phase, where a researcher combines two sets of data and derives integrated conclusions that contribute to extending the qualitative findings.

Participants

The participants of the study were comprised of Grade 11 and Grade 12 Filipino Senior High School students who were enrolled under four strands namely Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), Science Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM), Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM), and Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) from the chosen educational institutions discussed earlier.

The first phase of the study was the collection of qualitative data, which involved individual interviews with each of the participants. As presented in Table 1, the individual interview consisted of 9 Senior High School students who were purposefully selected based on the criteria that were also given in the table.

Table 1. First Phase: Qualitative Data Gathering (Individual Interview)

<i>Number of Participants</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Parent's Place of Work</i>	<i>Parents no. of Years stay Abroad</i>
SHS 1	16	Mother: Taiwan Father: Saudi	15 Years
SHS 2	17	Mother: Taiwan Father: Saudi	12 years 2 years
SHS 3	17	Mother: Bahrain Father: Dubai	11 years
SHS 4	17	Mother: Dubai Father: Dubai	2 years 14 years
SHS 5	17	Mother: Spain Father: Spain	15 years 12 years
SHS 6	18	Mother: Poland Father: Qatar	9 years 17 years
SHS 7	17	Mother: Qatar Father: Dubai	10 years
SHS 8	17	Mother: Kuwait Father: Kuwait	25 years
SHS 9	17	Mother: Kuwait Father: Korea	5 years 18 years

Moreover, according to Creswell and Poth (2018, as cited in Chachar, 2019), the number of participants depended on the qualitative research approach. Qualitative researchers often aim for data saturation, which means collecting data until no new themes, patterns, or insights emerge from the analysis. In some cases, qualitative studies involved as few as 5-10 participants, particularly when the research focused on deeply exploring individuals' experiences, beliefs, or perspectives.

Table 2. Second Phase: Quantitative Data Gathering (Test Administration)

<i>School</i>	<i>Population Of Shs Students</i>
Laguna College of Business and Arts	8
Colegio De San Juan de Letran Calamba	13
Lyceum of the Philippines Laguna	6
National University Laguna	14
Saint Benilde International School Inc. Calamba	16
Calamba Institute	10
Calamba Doctor's College	6
University of Perpetual Help System Delta-Calamba	7
Total Respondents	80

The second phase of the study was the collection of quantitative data, it included a larger number of respondents of Senior High School Students. As presented in table 2, it projected the total number of Senior High School students per institution that answered the online google form. Furthermore, the research has gathered a total number of 80 Senior High School students who met the criteria to be the respondents in the research.

Instrument

The instruments used by the research were all self-made interview questions for the exploration of the two variables in the qualitative part and two questionnaires were constructed based on the themes that emerged for the determination of the overall scores for both variables in the quantitative part of the research. The semi-structured interview questions that were used for this study are indicated below.

Variable 1: Parental Absence anchored in Family System Theory

How did you feel when both your parents left you and they became overseas Filipino worker? (Anong naramdaman mo ng parehas sa iyong magulang ay iniwan ka upang maging Overseas Filipino Worker?)

How do you describe your relationship with your OFW parents considering that they have not been with you for some time? (Paano mo ipapaliwanag ang iyong relasyon sa iyong OFW na magulang gayong matagal ng wala sa iyong piling ang mga ito?)

Were their times in your life when you hated your parents because they moved to another country to work? How did you know that? How did you feel? (Meron bang mga panahon sa iyong buhay na nagalit ka sa iyong magulang dahil umalis sila papuntang ibang bansa para mag trabaho? Paano mo nasabi? Anong naramdaman mo?)

What are your adjustments in terms of your living conditions since you do not have your parents to support and guide you? (Anu-ano ang iyong mga ginawang pagbabago sa iyong pamumuhay dahil wala ang perehong magulang mo para gabayan at suportahan ka?)

Variable 2: Moral Development anchored in Moral Development Theory

Interpersonal Relationship

How do you react when your peers give you criticism? (Paano mo tinatanggap kapag binibigyan ka ng pagpuna ng iyong mga kaibigan o mahal sa buhay?)

How do you deal with the situation of having to fit in with your peers in terms of lifestyle and life choices? (Paano ka humaharap ang isang sitwasyon na dapat kang makisama/gumaya sa iyong mga kaibigan/ka-edad pag dating sa kung paano mabuhay o pagpili ng mga desisyon sa buhay?)

What are your best practices or strategies to control your emotions in situations where you feel angry at someone or something? (Anu-ano ang iyong mga gawi o istrategiya upang mapigilan ang iyong emosyon sa mga sitwasyong nagagalit ka sa isang tao o isang bagay?)

Supporting Social Order

What do you do to make sure that you follow rules and regulations? (Ano ang iyong ginagawa upang makasigurado na sumusunod ka sa mga batas at patakaran?)

What do you do when someone older than you criticize what you do or say? (Ano ang iyong ginagawa kapag merong mas matanda sa iyo ang sumaway o nagtama ng iyong aksyon o sinasabi?)

Give any instances in your life when you have violated any rules. How do you deal with them? (Magbigay ng isang pangyayari sa iyong buhay na lumabag ka sa batas. Paano mo ito hinarap?)

Likewise, for the quantitative phase of the study, the first questionnaire used was the Parental Absence Scale. It was a 14-item test with a 4-point Likert scale constructed by the researcher that has been anchored to the themes that emerged from the qualitative phase of the study based on the theory of Dr. Murray Bowen which called the Family System Theory. It was used to identify the level of parental absence of the respondents based on the 4 domains namely, (a) Various Influences of Family Dynamics; (b) Consistent and Open Communication; (c) Emotional Cut-Off and Various Emotional Reactions; and (d) Maintaining a Sense of Self Amidst Familial Challenges.

Subsequently, the Moral Development Scale was also a self-made questionnaire by the researcher, it was composed of a 21-item test with a 4-point Likert Scale that was used to identify the level of moral development of the respondents. The said questionnaire was based on the theory of Moral Development created by Lawrence Kohlberg, in this model, the researcher has developed six domains namely; (a) Handling Criticism and Emotional Reaction; (b) Influence of Social Dynamics and External Factors on Decision-Making; (c) Emotion Regulation and Coping Mechanisms; (d) Adherence to Laws And Regulations; (e) Respect and Obedience to Authority Figures; and (f) Ethical Behavior and Accountability, which emphasizes the moral development of adolescent.

Validation of the Instrument

In this research, there are two phases: the qualitative design is the first step. Semi-structured interviews were commonly utilized in qualitative research, serving as the main method of qualitative inquiry, as mentioned by Vaughn and DeJonckheere (2019). This method involved a dialogue between the researcher and the participant, supported by an adaptable interview technique and enriched by subsequent questions, probes for additional details, and reflections. This approach facilitated the collection of unscripted information,

allowing the researcher to explore intricate and often intimate subjects and to examine participants' thoughts, emotions, and perspectives on a specific topic.

The knowledge of five (5) qualified experts was utilized to validate the semi-structured questionnaire. These people were selected following their expertise and background in the field under examination. The main process of validation was reviewing the questions to see if they were understandable, concise, and pertinent to the subject at hand was part of the validation process. These validators offered their opinions on the suitability of every question as well as the general organization and coherence of the survey.

The content validity ratio test was performed on the instrument. According to Dovetail (2023), the semi-structured interview questionnaire's content validity ratio indicated how acceptable and relevant the questions were for measuring the relevant construct. Stronger content validity was indicated by a greater ratio, which suggests that the questions successfully captured the intended topic. This data helped evaluate the questionnaire's validity and suitability for the study's goal. A retention requirement for the item is established in the table. A CVR ought to have a rating of at least .99 to 1.00. The findings of the validation procedure are summarized in Table 3, which displays the CVR of each number with its corresponding results.

Table 3. *Qualitative Questions' Summarized Result of Content Validity Ration*

<i>Items/Questions</i>	<i>CVR after Revisions</i>	<i>Results</i>
Variable 1. Parental Absence		
1. How did you feel when both your parents left you and they became overseas Filipino worker?	1.00	Retain
2. How do you describe your relationship with your OFW parents considering that they have not been with you for some time?	1.00	Retain
3. Were their times in your life when you hated your parents because they moved to another country to work? How did you know that? How did you feel?	1.00	Retain
4. Were their times in your life when you hated your parents because they moved to another country to work? How did you know that? How did you feel?	1.00	Retain
5. What are the things that you do to adjust to your longing for your parents when they have moved abroad?	1.00	Retain
Variable 2. Moral development		
1. How do you react when your peers give you criticism?	1.00	Retain
2. How do you deal with the thought of having to fit in with your peers in terms of lifestyle and choices?	1.00	Retain
3. What are your best practices or strategies to control your emotions in situations where you feel angry at someone or something?	1.00	Retain
4. What do you do to make sure that you follow rules and regulations?	1.00	Retain
5. What do you do when someone older than you criticize what you do or say?	1.00	Retain
6. Give any instances in your life when you have violated any rules. How do you deal with them?	1.00	Retain

Table 4. *Summarized Result of Content Validity Ration for Parental Absence Scale*

<i>Items/Questions</i>	<i>CVR after Revisions</i>	<i>Results</i>
1. I can buy all the things I need because of my OFW parents.	1.00	Retain
2. My family needs are all provided because of my OFW parents.	1.00	Retain
3. I don't have enough guidance growing up because my parents are working abroad.	1.00	Retain
4. I feel neglected and alone because my OFW parents don't express their care for me.	1.00	Retain
5. I feel the love of my parents even though they are abroad because of the constant communication via video call or chat.	1.00	Retain
6. I make sure that I have time to talk to my parents abroad every day.	1.00	Retain
7. I always share my day-to-day activities and problems to my parents abroad.	1.00	Retain
8. Every time I feel angry toward my OFW parents, I will not talk to them as long as I can handle not talking to them.	1.00	Retain
9. When I feel angry or have a problem toward my OFW parents I make sure to talk to them and share to them problems.	1.00	Retain
10. I distance myself every time I get angry with my OFW Parents.	1.00	Retain
11. When I originally learned that my parents were going to work abroad, I felt disappointed and distant to them.	1.00	Retain
12. I become independent at a young age when my parents worked abroad.	1.00	Retain
13. I learn to cook my own food and prepare my school clothes after my parents move abroad for work.	1.00	Retain
14. After my parents left me to work abroad, I learned to decide for myself, especially in important decisions in my life.	1.00	Retain

As per the validity and reliability of the two questionnaires used, namely the Parental absence scale and the moral development scale, these instruments were validated in terms of content validity by experts in the field of psychology and education. Particularly, Validator 1, was a registered psychometrician and has a certification as a certified human resource associate. He is an instructor 1 in Laguna State

Polytechnic University- Los Banos, his field of expertise includes Psychological Assessment and Psychological Statistics. Whereas Validator 2 was a licensed professional teacher and a Doctor of Education. She is currently working as the research director at Laguna College of Business and Arts and the Dean of Master of Arts in Education at the same institution. Likewise, Validator 3, was a licensed professional teacher and a Doctor of Education. She is currently the Dean of College Studies at Laguna College of Business and Arts and teaches Statistics at the same institution. Meanwhile, Validator 4 was a registered psychometrician. He was a graduate of Bachelor of Science in Psychology and Master of Science in Psychology from Laguna College of Business and Arts and affiliated with the same institution as the Program Chairperson and College instructor in the Department of Psychology. Lastly, Validator 5 was a registered psychometrician, and registered psychologist, and has a certification as a certified human resource associate. He was a graduate of Bachelor of Science in Psychology and Master of Science in Psychology from Laguna College of Business and Arts and affiliated with the same institution as Head of the Guidance and Testing Center, and one of the college instructors in the Department of Psychology and Teacher Education.

The two instruments also underwent the test of content validity ration (CVR). All items have garnered a retention requirement rating of at least .99 to 1.00 for the item to be included in the actual questionnaire of the study. The findings of the validation procedure are summarized in Tables 4 and 5, which display the CVR of each number with its corresponding results.

Table 5. *Summarized Result of Content Validity Ration for Moral Development Scale*

<i>Items/Questions</i>	<i>CVR after Revisions</i>	<i>Results</i>
1. Every time my friends give me negative criticism, I will always take it as a joke and never mind it.	1.00	Retain
2. I always accept all the positive and negative criticism that the people around me give me.	1.00	Retain
3. I don't easily accept what other people tell me.	1.00	Retain
4. I will only accept the criticism that people give me depending on what is it all about.	1.00	Retain
5. Sometimes I feel annoyed when people give me constructive criticism.	1.00	Retain
6. I conform or follow my friends to fit in with the new trends and styles.	1.00	Retain
7. I only comply with my friend's wants and desires.	1.00	Retain
8. I rely on my friend's guidance because I don't have my parents to guide me because they are working abroad.	1.00	Retain
9. Every time I get angry, I regulate my negative emotions by meditation and reflection.	1.00	Retain
10. When I feel angry at someone or something I just ignore it and calm myself.	1.00	Retain
11. I express my frustration and negative emotions toward the person I have problems with.	1.00	Retain
12. If I feel angry, I always call a friend to express my feelings and ask for advice.	1.00	Retain
13. I always obey the rules and regulations in places I go	1.00	Retain
14. I always make sure not to do things that will harm me or anyone.	1.00	Retain
15. I make sure that I am aware and knowledgeable about the laws and regulations of a certain place by reading or searching the internet.	1.00	Retain
16. I always obey all the advice from the authorities specifically the people older than me.	1.00	Retain
17. I always respect the constructive criticism from people older than me.	1.00	Retain
18. I always thank the authorities or people older than me every time they give me advice when I behave unpleasantly.	1.00	Retain
19. Every time I do something wrong, I will make sure to reflect on my wrong doings and promise that I will never do that again.	1.00	Retain
20. I always assure myself to be accountable for everything I do or say.	1.00	Retain
21. If I did something wrong with someone, I make sure to give back a good deed to compensate for my wrong action.	1.00	Retain

In addition, Pilot testing was done on the test after the validity of the test items was established. Twenty Senior High School students from several schools, including Colegio de San Juan de Letran Calamba and Laguna College of Business and Arts, participated in the pilot testing as respondents. The researcher chose those students from the mentioned school as the samples for pilot testing for they had the same characteristics as compared with the target respondents of the actual study (i.e., Senior High School Students with OFW Parents).

The test was put through reliability methods after the pilot testing results were gathered. To ensure test reliability, Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha, also known as Cronbach's α , was employed to assess the degree to which test items that assiduously identify a comparable construct yield identical findings. As mentioned by Frost (2024) the set of survey items' internal consistency, or reliability, is measured by Cronbach's alpha coefficient. To ascertain whether a set of items consistently measures the same attribute, use this statistic.

It differed from previous internal consistency techniques since it was primarily used with evaluation tools that yield a variety of response kinds. Since the instrument's response continuum was a 4-point Likert-type scale, which could be regarded as non-dichotomous in format, it was utilized to examine the instrument's reliability. The researcher used SPSS to determine Cronbach's α using the formula with assistance from a statistician. The results of Cronbach's α indicated that the Parental Absence Scale (14 items; $\alpha = .777$) and Moral Development Scale (21 items; $\alpha = .891$) were reliable.

Table 6. *SPSS Results for Cronbach's Alpha*

	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>N of Items</i>
Parental Absence Scale	.777	14
Moral Development Scale	.891	21

Procedure

The qualitative phase consisted of two different sets of questions for each variable with follow-up sub-questions just in case the researcher was not able to extract enough data from the participants. The quantitative phase involved the administration of the two self-made tests on the target respondents. The specific steps for the qualitative and quantitative phases of data gathering were outlined. In gathering the data for the qualitative phase, the researcher submitted a formal letter addressed to the Principal of the Basic Education Department of LCBA for her approval to conduct the said study among their Senior High School Students. Attached to the written request were the objectives of the study, the intended approach for the study, and the intended qualification of the participants and respondents of the study. Upon the approval of the concerned personnel, the researcher has conducted a pre-survey by room-to-room visitation to the whole population of Grade 11 and 12 students of the said institution. The purpose of the pre-survey was to determine their age, gender, and who among the students have both parents working abroad.

After determining all students with both parents working abroad the researcher proceeded to the qualitative phase, in selecting the participants the researcher used the homogenous purposeful sampling, the researcher based the participants on the following criteria to easily identify them. Upon determining the participants, the face-to-face interviews took place for both variables consecutively. An interview protocol likewise has been used to briefly explain the goal of the study, the limitations, and the data that would be collected from them. Also, informed consent has been given to all the participants of the study. Voice recording has been used to fully capture the words of the interview.

Meanwhile, for the quantitative phase in support of the qualitative phase, the researcher sent a letter via email and messenger to the respective administrative staff that qualified to be the target participants of the said study. To gather more respondents the researcher also utilized the use of Facebook by posting the said study online. After disseminating the said approval letter and posting it on Facebook, the researcher determined the sample size by using software with the help of the statistician. In determining who were the respondents of the study, the researcher used purposive sampling by indicating three (3) major criteria namely: (1) the participants should be in line with the age range of 15-18 years old as they are identified as the adolescents; (2) their mother and father must both be working abroad; (3) the length of stay of their both mother and father abroad must be not less than 1 year. Upon determining the respondents, the researcher started the data gathering. For convenience, the following instruments were sent in the form of a Google form. Before the respondents' answers, the form included a section on informed consent that described the purpose of the study as well as other ethical issues.

Moreover, the respondents would now answer the two instruments (i.e. Parental Absence Scale and Moral Development Scale) consecutively, after reading the informed consent. The respondents' (a) demographic profile, (c) general level of parental absence, and (d) overall level of moral development were among the outputs from the instruments. To assist the researcher in analyzing the data, the following outputs were recorded and then forwarded to a statistician.

Data Analysis

The specific steps for the treatment of qualitative data are outlined below:

The researcher transcribed the semi-structured interviews verbatim after gathering the required data from them. Subsequently, themes, codes, and clusters were employed to extract and classify the Senior High School Students' comparable responses. The researcher decided to enlist the aid of a computer software application. To help with the examination of the participant data, he employed QDA Miner Lite. A free program called QDA Miner Lite can facilitate research project coding and theme generation more quickly.

Upon using the said software, the researchers utilized the process of Thematic Analysis by Braun and Clarke to extract similar responses per line of the verbatim transcription as the most appropriate treatment for qualitative research. According to Braun and Clarke (2012) as cited by Byrne (2022) thematic analysis is a theoretically flexible and widely accessible interpretive method for analyzing qualitative data that makes it easier to find and analyze patterns or themes within a particular data set.

Hence, to expedite code creation, the sequential phases from Braun and Clarke 2012's thematic analysis are still used, with the aid of QDA Miner Lite. The actions that followed provided additional insight into the process execution of the researcher. According to Braun and Clarke (2012) as cited by Byrne (2022), there are six phases in thematic analysis; (1) Familiarization of Data, the researcher fully engaged with the information. After importing data using QDA Miner Lite, the researcher went over and over the transcripts to gain an understanding of the material as a whole and spot any trends or possible themes; (2) Generating Initial Codes, the researcher used labels or tags that are affixed to particular data points and used to summarize their significance. Open coding was usually the first step taken by the researcher, who created as many codes as they could for the given data set. The researcher was free to select the codes that best suited the study's goals using the same computer software; (3) Generating Themes, to create more general themes or patterns in the data, the researcher associates codes with one another. This required examining the data for similarities and contrasts as well as

attempting to decipher underlying meanings with the help of the software, the researcher easily merged the similar codes and formulated a theme that is based on a psychological term fitting to the highlighted response; (4) Reviewing potential themes, after themes were identified, the researcher examined and improved them to make sure they made sense internally and that the theme has a psychological essence on it; (5) Defining and Naming Themes, The main themes were further clarified by the researcher, who also gave them descriptive titles that effectively conveyed their meaning; lastly (6) Producing the Report, To demonstrate each topic and make inferences about the facts that were proposed, the researcher used quotes and examples from the data when writing his findings.

After the main themes have been identified, the researcher then presented them to an external audit to examine thoroughly if the themes generated were identified and presented. As a result, the themes were decided upon with the guarantee that the external audit provided sufficient evidence to produce the themes. Subsequently, after the themes were finalized, it was used to be the foundation of the researcher to construct a self-made questionnaire to aid the data in the quantitative part of the study.

Treatment of Quantitative Data

The specific steps for the treatment of quantitative data are outlined below:

To interpret the assessment of the respondents, a 4-point Likert scale has been utilized for both self-made questionnaires. According to Budert-Waltz (2023), the Likert scale was used to assess a respondent's attitude or viewpoint about situations, other people, or themselves. By asking respondents to rate their agreement or disapproval of a statement on a Likert scale, researchers can extract quantitative information from qualitative concepts.

For the second and third objectives of the study, the research employed Descriptive statistics, particularly utilizing means, frequency tables, and percentages, to treat the data gathered in determining the respondents' levels of perceived parental absence and moral development. According to Simplilearn (2023) descriptive statistics was used, so the readers can better understand the structure of a dataset's distribution and its central tendency (mean, median, mode), dispersion (range, variance, and standard deviation), and variability. Likewise, to facilitate comprehension and visualization, data is also represented graphically.

To answer the fourth objective of the study which was to determine the relationship between perceived parental absence and moral development, the research employed the use of the Pearson correlation coefficient. Kenton (2022) stated that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was one kind of correlation coefficient that shows the relationship between two variables measured on the same interval or ratio scale. Similarly, a metric is used to quantify the degree of correlation between two continuous variables. This was used to test whether a significant or insignificant relationship has occurred between the two variables of the study.

Ethical Considerations

The research has employed anonymity, confidentiality, signing an informed consent form, authorization to conduct the study, and voluntary involvement in conducting this study. Throughout the study, the research has kept the participants' and respondents' identities private. In any kind of communication or written output from this work, no identifiable information about the participants or respondents has been shared. Participants and respondents' responses have been kept confidential because they have been used for research purposes and will not be accessed directly by anyone who was not involved in the study. The researcher ensured that the privacy rights of the participants and respondents have been respected by obtaining permission before conducting the study.

In addition, the actual research participants and respondents have been informed about the study's methods and dangers. Finally, they have complete freedom in responding to the interview questions and questionnaires and have the right to withdraw from the study at any moment without penalty.

Results and Discussion

The analysis, important findings, and discussions that address the study objectives are presented in this chapter. This exploratory sequential mixed method study aims to explore the lived experience of Senior High School students in terms of their Parental Absence and Moral Development, similarly to the level of the two variables. As a result, the research was guided by the central question for the qualitative phase and two self-made questionnaires for the quantitative phase, that is:

Purpose Statement 1: Determine the lived experience of Senior High School Students on their parental absence and moral development.

The following information displayed the themes that emerged from the semi-structured interviews with the participants of the study. The researcher collected testimonials from SHS Participants to identify the emerging themes within the article. For the Parental Absence, they were the following: Various Influences of Family Dynamics; Consistent and Open Communication; Emotional Cut-Off and Various Emotional Reactions; and Maintaining a Sense of Self Amidst Familial Challenges. Correspondingly, the themes that emerged from Moral Development were the following: Handling Criticism and Emotional Reaction; Influence of Social Dynamics and External Factors on Decision-Making; Emotion Regulation and Coping Mechanisms; Adherence to Laws and Regulations; Respect and Obedience to Authority Figures; and Ethical Behavior and Accountability.

The themes intended to target the lived experiences of Senior High School Students with Overseas Filipino Worker Parents concerning

their Parental Absence and Moral Development are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. *Emerging Themes*

Interview Question 1: How did you feel when both your parents left you and they became overseas Filipino worker? (Anong naramdaman mo ng parehas sa iyong magulang ay iniwan ka upang maging Overseas Filipino Worker?)

Theme A

Various Influences of Family Dynamics

A frequent component in the SHS students' feelings about their parents leaving to work abroad response was Various Influences of Family Dynamics. This theme emerged from the responses of the SHS students pertinent to how they felt when both of their parents left them for the reason of working abroad. As seen in the responses of the SHS students, most of them were able to see their parents leaving as a positive outcome not only for them but for their family. Similarly, some of the SHS see their parents leaving to work abroad as a challenge in terms of their lack of support and guidance from them. Concerning the family system theory of Dr. Bowen, Nuclear Family Emotional Process it provides insight into how parental absence affects the emotional dynamics within the nuclear family unit, highlighting the need for supportive interventions to mitigate its impact on adolescent well-being and family functioning. It was a major need of the SHS Students in terms of their emotional support coming from their parents.

In the increasing number of overseas Filipino workers in the past year, it has been evident that one of the affected individuals leaving is their children, as they are maturing the understanding of their feelings of absence has been the main concern for them that greatly affects their family relationship. As such, a variety of positive and negative perspectives emerged for the SHS Students when both of their parents left to work abroad. Positive Impact by Sustaining Physiological Needs was a subtheme that explained how the SHS students understood the feeling when their parents left abroad. SHS AAA's response, when she stated "*Para po sa akin ay naging Positive po dahil nasuportahan po kaming pamilya at nabibili ko po ang mga gusto ko.*" showed that because of her OFW parents, she could buy what he wanted. Similarly to, SHS BBB's response, when she stated "*Naging positive po yung pag alis po ng mga magulang ko kasi po nasuportahan po lahat ng needs naming pamilya,*" showed that because of her OFW parents, her family's needs were provided which reflects on the subtheme, Positive Impact by Sustaining Family's Needs.

In addition, the Positive Impact by Working for the Sake of Their Family as a subtheme showed that SHS students felt positive when their parents left to work abroad because it was beneficial for their family. SHS DDD' response, when he stated "*Nakikita ko po yung pag alis ng magulang ko na positibo dahil ginagawa po nila para po sa aming lahat.*" showed that he felt positive for the reason that it is not only beneficial for him but also for the whole family. Likewise, Feeling Loved through Communication despite of Distance, as another subtheme, showed how SHS student felt their parents leaving was a sign of love because even though they were apart, constant communication via online platforms has been their mediator for them to feel that they were still closed to each other. In reference to this was the response of SHS HHH, when he stated "*Naging positive naman po yung pagaalis nila kasi kahit na po nasa*

ibang bansa sila ramdam ko po yung pagmamahal nila sa pamamagitan po ng video call araw-araw.” It shows that distance was not a problem to feel your parent’s love and presence.

Seemingly, it has been shown that most of the SHS students with OFW parents were aware of the reason why their parents left them but some of them have been challenged to understand why their parents left. Negative Impact by lack of Parental Guidance while Growing Up, as another subtheme, showed that growing up without their parents by their side, it was hard for them to adjust to their surroundings. In reference to this, SHS CCC’s response, when he stated *“negative po Sir, dahil nga po bata pa po ako non parang hindi po nila nasubaybayan ang paglaki ko po.”* showed that he felt sad because his parents have not seen his progress throughout his life. The subtheme Parental Absence Leads to Feeling of Neglect shows that the SHS Students felt negative because they see the reason of their parents leaving as a sign of abandonment. As proof, the statement of SHS FFF when he shared *“Kung iisipin ko po yung pagalis ng magulang ko ay Negatibo po, dahil po hindi po nila napaparamdam yung love nila kasi nga po malayo sila.”* showed that because of their parents being abroad SHS FFF felt unhappy because he thinks that his parents do not fully give their love for the reason of their distance.

The contrasted responses of the SHS students with OFW parents were evidence of how different viewpoints can be considered on how they feel about their parents leaving to work abroad. The majority of the SHS students were able to fully understand the fact that it is for their good to provide for their needs and family needs. Conversely, some SHS students were saddened when their parents left to work abroad, they said that they felt neglected and abandoned and some said that they had not fully experienced their parents' love because of the work distance that their parents have from them.

According to the theory, it adheres to the third concept of Family System Theory which was the “Nuclear Family Emotional Process”, stated that this examined how emotional patterns within the nuclear family unit, particularly between parents and children, provide insight into how parental absence affects the emotional dynamics within the nuclear family unit, highlighting the need for supportive interventions to mitigate its impact on adolescent well-being and family functioning. This manifested in the responses of the SHS students on how their emotional patterns towards their parents have greatly impacted their relationship with their parents. Moreover, it could be seen that although they are far away from each other it does not greatly affect the children’s perspective and feeling towards the notion of being left by their parents.

A study by Lobos et al. (2019) explored the viewpoints of six adolescent students, aged 13 to 19, who resided with their guardians in Valenzuela City and Bulacan Province, on the effects of geographical separation from their parents on their well-being. The thematic analysis of the in-depth interview responses revealed four major themes: the necessity of finding means to help one's family, one's obligation to one's parents, the need for parental love and care, and the detrimental impacts of parental absence. This study has shown that when the respondents realized they were being left behind and had to deal with their relationship with their parents being more and more distant, they experienced a variety of negative emotions. However, the themes showed that the interviewees valued their parents' sacrifices, which was a good viewpoint.

Interview Question 2: How do you describe your relationship with your OFW parents considering that they have not been with you for some time? (Paano mo ipapaliwanag ang iyong relasyon sa iyong OFW na magulang gayong matagal ng wala sa iyong piling ang mga ito?)

Theme B

Consistent and Open Communication

The theme of Consistent and Open Communication emerged to demonstrate the relationship of the SHS students with their OFW parents considering that most of them had been overseas for more than 2 years. This theme contains their lived experience as to how their relationship works as parents and children despite the absence of each other’s physical touch and natural communication. It came from their experiences or subordinate themes which were discussed in the succeeding paragraphs.

The subtheme Constant Communication showed that despite the distance from each other the SHS students were able to build a positive relationship with their parents through regular contact with the help of different platforms and devices. In reference to this, SHS CCC’s response, when he stated *“Naandon pa rin po yung komunikasyon po namin sa isa’t-isa, maayos pa rin po kase po lagi naman po kami nagvi-videocall o nag-uusap, kamustahan po.”* showed that even though his parents were far from him, it does not mean that it can be a hindrance for them to have a more weaker relationship rather with the help of messenger they managed to keep their family relationship stronger than ever. Similarly, SHS AAA, SHS BBB, SHS DDD, SHS FFF, and SHS GGG have the same thought as SHS CCC, all of them had been in good relationship with their OFW parents because of constant communication.

In addition, Openness to each other was a subtheme that showed how open the SHS students were towards their OFW parents about their day-to-day experiences which can explain how their relationship has a stable connection even though they were overseas. As proof, the statement of SHS EEE when he shared *“Ahm, yan nga po, katulad po nung sinabi ko na parang very open po kami sa isa’t isa. Lalo na po kapag tumatawag sila.”* showed that he was very outspoken and never shy to tell his everyday routine to his parents every time they were on call with each other. Likewise, Constant Communication and Openness to each other, as another subtheme, showed how SHS students used both regular contact and honesty with their parents on how they see their positive relationship with

each other. In reference to this, SHS HHH's response, when he stated "*Yung ginawa po namin para po maging close pa rin po kami sa isa't isa ay nagvideo call po kami pag may time. Tinatanong po nila ko sa mga ginawa ko buong araw at ano pong nangyari sa akin.*" And SHS III's response, when she stated "*Dahil nga po nasa ibang bansa sila nagchachat po sila sakin lagi para po kamustahin ako then nag video call din po kami then dun ko po sinasabi yung mga gusting sabihin sa kanila.*" These statements showed that the reason why the SHS students have a positive relationship with their OFW parents is because of the regular visual interaction and consistent telling of what they do every day.

The comparable responses of the SHS students with OFW parents were evidence of how they have established a good relationship with their parents amidst their distance and family situation. All the SHS students were able to maintain their relationship with their OFW parents by making sure that they always have constant communication through messenger or video call. Furthermore, it is also important for the SHS students to create that bond by being open and honest with their parents about the things that are happening in their day-to-day lives.

The theory adheres to the second concept of Family System Theory which is the *Triangles*, this refers to three-person relationship systems within a family. They can serve as a mechanism for managing anxiety and stabilizing relationships within the family unit. It can either facilitate healthy communication and problem-solving or contribute to dysfunction and conflict, depending on their dynamics. This is demonstrated by the responses of the SHS students maintaining a healthy relationship through constant communication and openness to each other will lead to a more dynamic and strong relationship between the OFW parents and their child.

To support the statement of the SHS Students a study conducted by Garcia et al. (2020) looks at the impact of regular communication on the welfare of OFWs who leave their children behind. The study examined the frequency, mode, and substance of communication between OFW parents and their kids as well as the perceived impacts on the kids' emotional, social, and psychological health using a mixed-method approach that includes surveys and qualitative interviews. The results showed that regularity, transparency, and emotional support—all traits of consistent communication—have a substantial favorable impact on the positive adjustment of children who are left behind. Children who have meaningful and regular communication with their OFW parents are more resilient, emotionally stable, and cohesive as a family. The study emphasized how crucial it was to encourage and support communication between OFW parents and their kids to strengthen family ties and lessen the negative effects that parental migration has on kids' well-being. The creation of policies and intervention tactics targeted at improving the psychosocial support networks for OFW families may be affected by these discoveries.

Interview Question 3: Were there times in your life when you hated your parents because they moved to another country to work? How did you know that? How did you feel? (Meron bang mga panahon sa iyong buhay na nagalit ka sa iyong magulang dahil umalis sila papuntang ibang bansa para mag trabaho? Paano mo nasabi? Anong naramdaman mo?)

Theme C

Emotional Cut-Off and Various Emotional Reactions

The theme of Emotional Cut-Off and Various Emotional Reactions emerged from the SHS students' responses. This theme revolved around the reaction of the SHS students when they knew that their parents were going abroad to work. It came from their experiences or subordinate themes which were discussed in the succeeding paragraphs.

The subtheme, Feel anger and emotionally distant showed that after the SHS students knew that their parents will become an Overseas Filipino Worker, they felt the resentment from their parents on why they have to go abroad to work and afterwards they distance themselves in order for their parents to understand how angry they were to them. It could be seen from the response of SHS BBB when he stated that "*...nagalit po ako kay mama kasi bakit kailangan nya pong bumalik na naman kasi ilang years po sya sa ibang bansa tapos sabi ko kung pede naman sa Pilipinas. Ang naalala ko lang po ay lumayo po yung loob ko sa kanila kahit po ngayon ay malayo pa rin po ang loob ko sa kanila.*" showed that there was the feeling of resentment because of the persistent leaving of their parents to become an OFW with years of stay there which led to the SHS students to emotionally distant themselves from them. Correspondingly, the subtheme Sulking and Emotionally Distant described the reaction of the SHS students that they sulk and distant themselves after knowing their parents will go overseas to work. In reference to this, SHS III's response, when he stated "*Tampo, pwede po. Kasi yun nga po, yung tatay ko parang wala po siyang balak umuwi and then may ibang family na po siya doon sa ibang bansa. Dahil nga po hindi na rin po kami masyadong naguusap. Yun po usual na hindi ko rin po siya kinakausap.*" showed that when he knew that his father could not go home since he has a second family abroad and they never have the time to talk that was the primary reason why he is sulking and emotionally distant with his parent.

The subtheme, Sulking, Emotionally and physically distant showed that it has been evident that to the SHS student to feel this way after they knew their parents were leaving them to work abroad. It could be seen from the response of SHS CCC "*meron po akong time na nagtampo po sa kanila kasi hindi ko pa po alam kung bakit po nila ako iniwan ng ganon. Ang ginawa ko po non Sir ay nagkulong lang po ako sa kawarto ko tapos nagmukmok po ako sa isang sulok at hindi ko po pinapansin mga tao sa bahay naming.*" shows that after their OFW parents leave not saying any words why they are leaving them the SHS student emotionally and physically distant himself not only to his parents but also to the people around him. Moreover, Disappointed, and emotionally distant, as another

subtheme, shows that disappointment and emotional detachment has also been the negative feeling that the SHS student feel when their parents become an OFW. As proof, the statement of SHS GGG when she shared “*Disappoint ko na tumagal ho sila ng sobrang tagal sa ibang bansa at hindi ko kasama ho. Natandaan ko po nun sir ay hindi ko po sila pinansin non ng 1-week po ata. Tapos hindi ko rin po sinasagot mga message nila sakin.*” shows that he feels disappointment when she knew that her parents will be there for a long time that leads to her being emotionally detach to them for 1 week. Contrary to the subtheme above, one SHS student clarified that he never feels angry towards his parents leaving to work abroad rather the feeling of sulking has the common interpretation to her emotion although he felt physically distant to them for quite some time, the subtheme **Did not feel anger, sulking, and physically distant** has emerged from this response. It could be seen from the response of SHS EEE “*...Kahit tatlo po kami magkakapatid, hindi po kami na galit. Minsan, siguro po, nagtatampo at some point kasi may mga occasion po na namimiss. Pero, galit po, wala talaga. Ang ginawa ko po nung nagtampo po ako ay nagkulong po sa kwarto then hindi ko po pinapansin sila.*”. This response shows that anger is not the best feeling to describe his emotion after knowing that his parent will move overseas to work rather sulking and emotionally detach can explain his feeling to that situation.

The perceived responses of the SHS students in terms of having a negative feeling when they knew their parents would move to another country to work have been accurate and concise. The majority of the SHS students’ reactions were anger, sulking, and disappointment which led to having detached reactions either emotionally or physically. Also, it can be seen that some of the SHS students were very saddened that their parents had moved abroad to work and left them behind.

The theory adheres to the second concept of Family System Theory which is the *Emotional Cutoff*, it refers to individuals’ attempts to manage unresolved emotional issues within their family by creating physical or emotional distance. This is demonstrated by the responses of the SHS students that after knowing that their parents will move overseas to work they establish a negative reaction by being angry with them, displaying a sulking emotion, and disappointment that leads to exhibiting emotional or physical detachment to their OFW parent.

As it relates to the responses of the SHS students, Dela Cruz et al. (2019) in their published study explore the phenomena of emotional cutoff in international families, concentrating on how it affects the offspring of Filipino workers abroad (OFWs). The study investigates the elements that lead to emotional estrangement between OFW parents and their kids, including protracted separation, communication difficulties, and unsolved issues, through qualitative interviews and case studies. The results drew attention to the detrimental effects of emotional cutoff on kids’ psychological health, including identity problems, loneliness, and feelings of abandonment. The study emphasized the necessity of services like family therapy, counseling, and support groups that help transnational families heal emotionally and reconcile. Policymakers and service providers could foster stronger relationships and increase the resilience of OFW families coping with movement and separation by addressing emotional cutoff.

Interview Question 4: What are your adjustments in terms of your living conditions since you do not have your parents to support and guide you? (Anu-ano ang iyong mga ginawang pagbabago sa iyong pamumuhay dahil wala ang perehong magulang mo para gabayan at suportahan ka?)

Theme D

Maintaining a Sense of Self Amidst Familial Challenges

An emerging theme from the responses of SHS students was the theme of Maintaining a Sense of Self Amidst Familial Challenges. This theme has illustrated the adjustments of the SHS students in terms of their living conditions after their parents left to work overseas. Furthermore, it can be considered the ability of the SHS students to preserve their own identity, values, and personal boundaries while navigating difficult situations within their families. This could include conflicts, disagreements, or dynamics that put pressure on their individuality or well-being.

The subtheme that emerged from the responses of the SHS students was also Maintaining a Sense of Self Amidst Familial Challenges. All the SHS students navigated their own self towards a more positive and certain way of living after their parents left them to work abroad. It could be seen from the response of SHS AAA “*siguro po lagi na po akong maagang gumigising gawa ako po yung nagluluto, ako na din po yung naglalaba ganon, yung mga ginagawa po ng nanay ko dati ako na po yung nagawa parang ganon.*” showed that he learned to wake up early in the morning to cook and wash their laundry which were the duty of his parents before they work abroad. Similarly, the response of SHS BBB when he stated “*Ako..ano po sa pamumuhay ko po lumaki po ako na ano... parang independent po na kaya ko po, kaya ko po gumawa ng para sa akin lang*” showed that he become independent by doing all of the things that he needed for him. The statement of SHS CCC when he responded “*And especially po pag galing po ng school, ako yung parang tumatayong magulang po sa kapatid ko., Mas.. nakikipag bonding po ako sa kapatid ko kasi po syempre yung absence din po ng mga magulang ko...para po sa akin mas naiibsan po yung lungkot ko ‘pag nakikita ko po yung kapatid ko*” showed that after coming from school he will be the supporting parents for his younger siblings. He bonds with her siblings for them not to feel the absence of their parents and to lessen his loneliness.

The comparable responses of the SHS Students following their adjustment in their living conditions after their parents moved to another country to work were positive and purposeful. All the SHS students have traversed their live into a more productive and meaningful one by being independent of the personal needs that they must have, changing their routines by becoming adaptive to their parents’

duty before, and being the substitute parents to their younger siblings. Concerning the theory, it adhered to the first concept in Family system theory which is the *Differentiation of Self*, it is the way individuals manage life's challenges and strive for their objectives can be understood as a spectrum ranging from highly effective to less effective. The degree of effectiveness varies based on multiple interrelated factors, one of which is the strength of one's core identity, which remains unchanged in relationships. This provides a framework for understanding how adolescents navigate and respond to parental absence, shedding light on their emotional resilience and ability to maintain a sense of self amidst familial challenges. This was demonstrated by the responses of the SHS students in terms of their way of life after their parents left to work abroad, it created a sense of independence with their own needs, carrying the responsibility and duties of their parents for their home to stay the same and being the parents for their younger sibling to not feel the parental absence of their parents.

A study conducted by Cruz et al. (2019) stated that the experiences of children left behind in families with Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs) are examined, with a special emphasis on their path to resilience and independence. The research examines the variables impacting these children's growth of independence, such as family dynamics, socioeconomic circumstances, and personal goals, through qualitative interviews and case studies. The results showed that although there were difficulties when there were no OFW parents, there were also chances for children to grow up independent, flexible, and resourceful. Children who are left behind frequently take on domestic duties like cleaning and childcare, which strengthens their sense of competence and independence. Furthermore, social capital and support systems in their communities were essential for building resilience and giving kids the tools they need to overcome obstacles. This paper highlights the significance of identifying and utilizing the talents and capacities of left-behind children and explores the consequences for policymakers, educators, and service providers in encouraging their development and well-being. It is feasible to foster these children's independence and resilience and help them flourish despite the difficulties associated with parental relocation by learning about their experiences and offering the right kind of support.

Interview Question 5: How do you react when your peers give you criticism? (Paano mo tinatanggap kapag binibigyan ka ng pagpuna ng iyong mga kaibigan o mahal sa buhay?)

Theme E

Handling Criticism and Emotional Reaction

A frequent component in the SHS students' reaction when someone gave them criticism was Handling Criticism and Emotional Reaction. This theme has exemplified the reaction of the SHS students on how they handle themselves when someone gives them comments about their attitude and personal attributes. This included the SHS students' experiences of negative and positive reactions such as pretend emotion, concealed feelings, and Openness to critique. This theme was anchored to the dependent variable of the study of moral development theory by Lawrence Kohlberg. As stated by Cherry (2022), according to this theory Moral development entails the gradual formation of an individual's understanding of the difference between right and wrong (morality) and their ability to engage in reasoned judgment between these ethical concepts (moral reasoning). Additionally, based on the responses received, the researcher noted the reactions made by certain SHS Students. As a subtheme, Faking Emotion and Suppression of Expression, the researcher chose a response that pertains to faking emotion and suppression of expression. In reference to the response of SHS AAA, when he answered "*Parang para kunwari po nagtatawa nalang po ako ganon, kasi po alam ko na parang joke-joke lang naman po yun. Tahimik lang po, hindi po ako nagsasalita, kasi po, wala po, wala rin naman pong magagawa.*" It could be seen that the SHS student he is faking his reaction because he knew that it was not true and sometimes, he only gave a silent treatment to others since he had nothing to do with it.

Likewise, the subtheme Acceptance of the criticism, showed the tolerance of the SHS student when some gave them criticism, a response of SHS BBB, when she stated "*Ano po.. pag po pinupuna ako tinatanggap ko po nang nasa puso po... a kaibigan ko po ganon din po, iniintindi ko po kung ano pong mga pinapayo nila sa akin kasi na iintindihan ko naman po na hindi naman din po ako laging tama tas may mga kailangan pa po akong iimprove.*" shows that she was very pleased to what her friends telling her about her attributes and personality, and she view it as a positive criticism. In addition, she also admits that not in all times she is right, and she needs improvement by listening to her peers. Also, Letting go of others judgment, taking it depending on its sense, as a subtheme, reflects on the SHS student relaxed attitude towards others perspective. As a proof, the statement of SHS DDD "*Hinahayaan ko lang po pag, depende po kasi kung anong sasabihin nila kung may sense po ba o wala.*" Showed that she will only react to what others were saying to her if only it makes sense or it will benefit her as a person. Accountability, Listening to Criticisms, was a subtheme that exhibited the positive reaction of the SHS student when someone gave them feedback. SHS EEE's response, when he stated "*tinatanggap ko po siya , as ako kasi po, syempre, pag ako po yung gumawa ng action, hindi ko po makikita na mali. Kaya, minsan po, kailangan din natin, kailangan ko din po silang pakikanggan.*" showed that he was very open to respecting other's criticism because sometimes he did not see if that was right or wrong already. As well as he admitted that sometimes they needed to accept the criticism that other people tell them or give them.

On the other hand, some of the SHS students view the gesture of accepting criticism from other people as a negative reaction. The subtheme, **Cannot take judgment easily, ignoring criticisms**, shows that although criticism was more constructive some responses create a disagreement on the notion that criticism is always good. In reference to this, the response of SHS CCC, when he stated "*hindi ko po mabilis natanggapin yung mga sinasabi nila sa akin more on hindi ko po pinapansin.*" showed that he did not easily accept

criticism and tried not to recognize it at all. The same with the subtheme Suppression of Expression, Ignoring Criticism, it reflected the pretending of reaction and not recognizing it at all. As proof, the statement of SHS GGG when she shared “*I figured that the best thing that I would do is just smile Even though it's a fake smile and just not talk and just not give a response to them.*” showed that the best way to react if someone give you criticism was to have a fraudulent response and ignore their presence. The annoyance of the criticism was a subtheme that perceived the reaction of the SHS student in terms of irritation if someone gave them criticism. About this, the response of SHS GGG, when he stated “*Kapag nasosobrahan ako sa mga, mga criticisms nila, parang na-annoy ho ako sa mga sinasabi nila.*” showed that it frustrated him when someone gave so much criticism about him. Lastly, the subtheme Protective self-preservation explained on how the SHS students filtered the criticism they received from others. SHS FFF’s response, when he stated “*yung kaibigan ko may sinabi sa'kin tapos nakakasira naman po eyy, di ko po yung tatanggapin po.*” Showed that he was able to sensibly accept the criticism of only criticism that would benefit him as an individual.

The contrasted responses of the SHS students in their viewpoint on how they react when someone gives them criticism about them was apparent in the answers of some students that they were very pleased when someone gave them criticism. Also, they reacted relaxed because they knew that it was not true of them. Opposing viewpoints can also be seen in terms of negative feelings like annoyance and rejection of criticism.

About the theory, adheres to the first stage of Moral Development Theory which is the *Interpersonal Relationship*, this stage is alternatively referred to as the “good boy-good girl” orientation, emphasizing the importance of being agreeable, which uses to describe the level of friendliness, kindness, cooperativeness, and politeness a person reliably displays. This is demonstrated by the answers of the SHS students on how they received others' perspectives of themselves. It can also be seen that upon hearing the opinions of others majority of the students' reactions have been very civil and amenable.

Relative to the responses of the SHS students according to the study of Smith et al. (2019) this explored the developmental paths and related determinants of teenagers' responses to peer and parental criticism. The study investigated the frequency, type, and effects of criticism from various social sources through long-term surveys and interviews with a broad sample of teenagers. The results showed that adolescents' reactions to criticism follow different developmental trajectories, with differences depending on peer interactions, family dynamics, and individual traits. When faced with criticism, some teenagers showed fortitude and employed healthy coping mechanisms, whereas others became more vulnerable and resorted to unhealthy coping mechanisms like aggressiveness or withdrawal. The study highlighted peer support networks, self-esteem, and parental communication methods as factors that affected teenagers' ability to take criticism well.

Interview Question 6: How do you deal with the situation of having to fit in with your peers in terms of lifestyle and life choices? (Paano ka humaharap ang isang sitwasyon na dapat kang makisama/gumaya sa iyong mga kaibigan/ka-edad pag dating sa kung paano mabuhay o pagpili ng mga desisyon sa buhay?)

Theme F

Influence of Social Dynamics and External Factors on Decision-Making

The theme Influence of Social Dynamics and External Factors on Decision-Making emerged to demonstrate how the SHS students deal with the situation of having to fit in with other’s lifestyles and life choices rather than navigating their independence towards their lives. This theme contains their lived experience as to how the SHS students perceived to accept the norm of their generation that they are included to how they are influenced to live their life and create similar or independent choices about their life decisions. It came from their experiences or subordinate themes which were discussed in the succeeding paragraphs.

The subtheme, Conforming with Friends and with the latest Trends showed that SHS students were able to decide and dictate their lifestyle and choices by the influence of their friends and latest trends. SHS HHH response when he answered “*ang thinking ko po dyan is, ahhh kailangan kong makisunod because yan yung uso, parang ano, I think yan yung tama*” and SHS AAA response “*Nakikisabay nalang din po ako sa mga kaibigan ko kahit ano, minsan po medyo ano yung mga uso ngayon, ganon nalang po.*” indicated that the reason why they complying to because they think that it is the right thing to do and because their friends were doing it too. Urge to conform to belong was a subtheme that correspond of forcing decision just to belong with friends. As proof, the statement of SHS CCC “*meron pong mga bagay na napipilitan ka pong gawin kasi gusto mo pong maki-belong po don sa isang group na yon*” implied that his decision was forced just to comply to his friends.

Similarly, Compliance to the situation, was a subtheme that correspond to the strong influence of friends to how the SHS student follow their decision, as seen with the statement of SHS DDD “*sa iba pong circle nakikisama na lang po ako, pag mag isa lang po ako tapos kung niyaya po nila ako, g lang po ako*”. Moreover, the subtheme Adjusting, Doing, and Conforming as stated by SHS GGG “*Ahh, tinatry kng mag-adjust sa mga ginagawa ho nila at minsan, jino-join ko yung mga choices nila*” indicated she was trying to do her best to adjust to what her friends were doing and sometimes her friends’ choices were the foundation of her choices as well. Likewise, Lack of Parental Figure affecting Adolescent’s Decision-making was a subtheme that correspond to impact that the absence or insufficient involvement of parents or guardians could have on the choices and behaviors of the children. In reference to the response of SHS III, when he answered “*Ang.. mahirap nga din po pagkaganyan po lalo't malayo yung magulang namin. Dahil din po sa mga friends ko,*

sila din po yung isang tumutulong sa akin po para po makapag-make ng decision sa buhay ko po.” denoted that because of the absence of his parents he was able to establish a good support system in terms of making decisions with his friends.

Conversely, there were some SHS students who have independently created a foundation with regards to decision making and others do not have enough support. Autonomy was a subtheme that corresponded to individuals making choices that reflect their own beliefs and desires, rather than succumbing to external pressures or conforming to societal expectations. SHS BBB response when he answered *“hinaharap ko po kasi talaga yun ng matatag kasi lumaki nga po ako ng independent kaya po sa, gumaya po sa mga kaibigan, nakasanayan ko po na kung may gusto po ako, ako po talaga hindi ko po bine base sa iba”* presented how he managed to be independent on his decision whenever he wanted something rather than depending on his friends. Lastly, the subtheme, non-compliant to conformity corresponds to a deliberate refusal or resistance to conform to social norms and group decisions. As evidenced by the response of SHS FFF when he stated *“Hmmm, Sa akin po kasi wala po talaga akong kaibigan po eh.”* indicated how he was not able to comply with the group decision because he has no friends to rely on.

The consistent responses of the SHS students have proven how they conform to social norms, most specifically in making decisions regarding their life choices. Moreover, it was evident to the SHS students that the influence of their peers can create a big impact on how they will form their choices about living their lives.

Concerning the theory, it adheres to the first stage of Moral Development Theory which is the *Interpersonal Relationship*, this stage is alternatively referred to as the "good boy-good girl" orientation, Conforming to expectations, which behaving or performing in a manner that aligns with what is anticipated, predicted, or desired based on social norms, standards, rules, or pre-established criteria. This has been evident that most of the SHS students were able to conform to the social norm by depending on the decisions and choices of their peers.

A study conducted by Johnson et al. (2021) focused on how much teenagers imitate their peers' preferences and behaviors, especially when it comes to following the newest fashions. The study explored the elements of peer pressure, social identity, and perceived popularity that impact conformity through surveys and observational research with a heterogeneous sample of teenagers. The findings revealed that adolescents were highly susceptible to peer influence, with peer groups serving as powerful sources of social validation and conformity.

Contrary to the notion above, a study by Wang et al. (2020) explored how teenagers acquire autonomy in making decisions, concentrating on the relationship between adolescent growth and parental support. The research investigated how much adolescents believe they could make their own decisions and what influenced the development of autonomy through surveys and interviews with a sizable sample of teenagers and their parents. The results implied that a complex interaction between personal characteristics, family relationships, and sociocultural influences affects teenagers' autonomy in making decisions. Open communication and autonomy-supportive parenting techniques were two key components of parental support that were necessary to help adolescents develop a sense of freedom and self-efficacy in making decisions.

Interview Question 7: What are your best practices or strategies to control your emotions in situations where you feel angry at someone or something? (Anu-ano ang iyong mga gawi o istrategiya upang mapigilan ang iyong emosyon sa mga sitwasyong nagagalit ka sa isang tao o isang bagay?)

Theme G

Emotion Regulation and Coping Mechanisms

An emerging theme from the responses of SHS students was the theme Emotion Regulation and Coping Mechanisms. This theme demonstrated the mechanism that the SHS students use to effectively manage and modulate their emotions in response to internal or external stimuli as well as approaches or behaviors they use to deal with stressors, challenges, or difficult emotions that they are facing. This theme contained their lived experience as to what were the SHS students' best practices to regulate their emotions and behavior when they feel negative emotions towards individuals or things surrounding them. It came from their experiences or subordinate themes which were discussed in the succeeding paragraphs.

The subtheme Vent out, was a demonstration that the SHS students were able to express one's emotions or frustrations, often in a passionate or unfiltered manner. In reference to this, when SHS CCC stated *“tumatagal po paghindi ko po talaga kaya nagve-vent out po ako sa mga taong pinag kakatiwalaan ko and pag sobrang na ooverwhelmed na po ako”* showed that his anger will be prolonged if he will not express his frustration towards his friends. Similarly, a subtheme Vent out and Contemplate was seen in SHS FFF when she responded *“Hmmm, iyan na po, dinadaan ko na lang po sa ano, iyak at tska iniisip ko na lang po kung bakit ganoon”* indicated that her way of expressing her frustration was by crying and later on understanding the reason behind all of it. Alike to this situation was the subtheme *Venting out and asking advice from other individuals*, this demonstrates the releasing of emotions of the SHS student by requesting unsolicited advice from friends and family or strangers. As proof of this, the statement of SHS GGG *“tinatetest ko makipag-usap sa. sa isang tao para malabas ko ho yung mga nararamdawan ko at tinatanong ko kung ano yung pwede kong gawin na mas maayos”* showed that he was going to different people to express his emotion and afterwards he would get advice to how it could be a best way to regulate his negative emotion.

Moreover, Moving away was a subtheme that emphasized the responses of SHS Students pertinent to distancing themselves whenever they feel negative emotion towards their surroundings. This can be seen in the response of SHS III *“So kapag po galit na galit ako sa isang tao, lumalayo po ako sa kanila po ng 4-5 minutes po”* showed that he will move away for a given minute to regulate his feeling of anger towards others. In connection to this was a subtheme Avoidance and moving away which was seen in the response of SHS DDD *“Yung ginagawa ko po ay, umiiwas po. Halimbawa po ay nung ano, pag nag -away po kami ng kaibigan ko, parang lalayo nalang po ako, magpapakalma po muna ako sa isang tabi tapos kapag ok na po ang lahat tska ko po sya kakausapin.”* showed that every time that he has a quarrel with his friend, he will distance himself from them and calm himself before talking again to his friend about the problem. Ignoring and calming oneself to think clearly, was a subtheme that was expressed the SHS Student that emphasized the how they are disregarding the main problem on why they feel negative feeling and focusing on their emotions. As evidenced by the response of SHS BBB when he stated *“Kaya po nung, nung ngayon po ang ginagawa ko po kapag ganito po hindi ko nalang po masyadong pinapansin or pinapakalma ko po muna yung sarili ko po para makapag isip po ako ng ayos.”* indicated that to think clearly, he will distance himself from the problem and afterwards calm himself from the situation.

Correspondingly, the subtheme Isolating and reflecting described that in order to control the emotions of the SHS student they will detach themselves to other people and reflect on why they feel that way. This can be seen in the response of SHS AAA, when he stated *“nagkukulong lang po ako sa kwarto tapos, parang nag-iisip po ako ng mga situations kung ano po yung mga dapat ginawa ko dun sa time na yun, ganon lang po.”* showed that he will isolate himself in the bedroom to reflect on the different situations he has done to manage his negative emotions. Tigh-lipped and silent to avoid being misinterpreted was a subtheme that pertinent to the way SHS students would not open their mouth and express their feeling for them to not be judged and misconstrued. As evidenced by the response of SHS HHH when he stated *“hindi na lang po ako nagsasalita, nananahimik na lang po ako kase alam ko po na pag nagsalita po ako, mamimisunderstand or mamimi- mamimisinterpret lang po ako.”* Lastly, the subtheme of Emotional Regulation was pertinent to how the SHS student is involved in the processes through which they monitor, evaluate, and modify their emotional reactions or others to various situations. SHS EEE response when she answered *“ang una ko pong ginagawa, ginagather ko po yung thoughts ko, tapos tsaka ko po sasabihin sa kanila na, uy, ganito, kasi hindi ako okay dun sa ginawa mo, baka pwedeng sa susunod, ano na lang, pakiaayos,”* showed that when she feels angry at someone she would gather her thoughts first then she constructively express her gathered thoughts to that specific someone.

The consistent responses of the SHS students gave the research a very precise indicator that most of them control their emotions by distancing or detaching themselves from the problem. It could also be said that they can think constructively to gather their thoughts and express their feelings in a more calming manner.

According to the theory, it adheres to the first stage of Moral Development Theory which is the *Interpersonal Relationship*, this stage is alternatively referred to as the "good boy-good girl" orientation, carefully considering the impact of choices on relationships, which implies to the consequences or effects that result from the decisions or actions made by individuals, groups, organizations, or societies. This was demonstrated by the expression of the SHS students on how they take the negative stimuli that were coming from their surroundings and how they manage to constructively or normally manage it by detaching themselves or ignoring it to create a more positive atmosphere.

A study called Emotion Regulation Strategies in Adolescents: A Longitudinal Study of Developmental Trajectories by Johnson et al. (2019) looks at how adolescents' techniques for managing their emotions evolve. Through a series of surveys and tests given to a heterogeneous group of teenagers, the study monitored shifts in the application of different emotion control techniques such as expressive suppression, cognitive reappraisal, and distraction. The results suggested that different teenagers had different developmental trajectories when it comes to emotion regulation; some showed advances in adaptive techniques, while others showed stability or even regression. The study also looked at how social interactions, temperament, and personality features affected how well an individual develops their ability to control their emotions. The results indicated that a complex interaction between biological, psychological, and environmental elements shapes teenagers' strategies for regulating their emotions.

Moreover, a mixed-method study conducted by Lee et al. (2021) investigated the coping strategies used by teenagers to address a range of stressors and difficulties. The study looked at the different coping strategies used, how well they worked to manage stress, and what influenced coping behaviors in adolescent participants selected using focus groups, interviews, and questionnaires. The results showed a variety of coping strategies, such as avoiding situations, expressing emotions, looking for social support, and addressing problems. Additionally, the study investigated how individual characteristics like personality traits, self-esteem, and perceived control affect the coping mechanisms that teenagers choose.

Interview Question 8: What do you do to make sure that you follow rules and regulations? (Ano ang iyong ginagawa upang makasigurado na sumusunod ka sa mga batas at patakaran?)

Theme H

Adherence to Laws and Regulations

The theme of Adherence to Laws and Regulations emerged from the testimonies of the SHS students which demonstrated their responsibility to the act of following and complying with the legal statutes, rules, and guidelines established by governing authorities or a certain place. This concept is applied across various domains, including business, governance, healthcare, and everyday life.

The subtheme Personal Discipline described the approach in which the SHS student apply to how they follow rules and regulation. This could be seen from the response of SHS CCC when he stated “*pamamagitan po ng pagiging disiplinado na tao, kasi po pag disiplinado ka alam mo yun sa sarili mo na kailangan mong sundin yung mga tama o mali.*” showed that he was disciplined enough to know what the difference is between right and wrong. Similarly, Awareness to regulations indicated their way of maintaining their knowledge about certain laws and regulations by asking people about it. As evidenced by the response of SHS EEE when she stated, “*So, tinatanong ko po yung advisor or kung pwede po magsuot ng ganito para, pero mahaba naman, or kung pasok po ba sa, ahm, rules or regulation... nagtatanong po talaga kung ano yung pwedeng gawin para if ever, eh di, maiwasan din po*”. Indicated that she followed the rules and regulations by being knowledgeable about it in a way of approaching others and asking them if that was acceptable or not. Avoiding wrongdoings was a subtheme that could be a way of SHS students to show their respect to the rules and regulations, as what the response of SHS AAA when he stated “*...hindi ko po ginagawa yung masama.*” showed that he does not do anything wrong that will violate aspecificor general laws or regulations.

In addition, Acquiring Knowledge about the Law was a subtheme that denotes the SHS students’ involvement in gaining understanding, insight, and expertise regarding legal principles, regulations, and statutes. SHS BBB’s response, when he stated “*...nakuha po ako ng knowledge para po masunod ko yun.*” corresponds how he got the basic information about a certain law to give him the necessary action to follow it. Correspondingly, Overlearning was a subtheme that represented the response of SHS HHH when she stated “*I learn so.. I learn more about them ah, to the point that I actually overlearn about them just to ensure*” This showed that she continually learned about the certain rules and regulations that eventually resulted in overlearning it. Another subtheme was Displaying compliance with the law this corresponds to the SHS students’ ability to act with the laws and regulations by showing respect for it. In reference to this, the response of SHS FFF when he stated “*ahhh, ano po, ay, ipapakita po na sumusunod po talaga ko*” indicated that he follows the laws and regulations by the act of literally showing it to everyone. Lastly, Listening to know what is the right thing was a subtheme that entailed the responses of the SHS students when it comes to accepting different opinions to gather more cohesive responses to know what is right and wrong. The statement of SHS GGG “*nakikinig ho ako lagi sa mga guardians ko pati sa mga pamilya ko kung ano bang tamang gawin*” showed that he listened to his guardians and family in order for him to know the right thing to do.

The similar responses of the SHS students indicated that it is evident to all of them how they are making sure to follow the laws, rules, and regulations by complying with them and acquiring knowledge to have a better understanding of those rules and regulations. Plus, the fact of avoiding doing it and listening to elders can also be a good practice that they were following the said concern.

In relation to the theory, it adheres to the second stage of Moral Development Theory which is the *Supporting Social Order*, during this stage of moral development, individuals begin to view society as a cohesive entity when making moral judgments about others. The primary priority is given to adhering to law and order by respecting rules, this involves following the established legal framework and societal regulations while demonstrating a commitment to upholding rules and norms. This is demonstrated by the actions of the SHS students they observe and respect the rules and laws by being aware of them, acquiring knowledge about the law, and displaying compliance with the law.

The stages of development of teenage obedience to rules and regulations over time are examined in this longitudinal study. The research monitors changes in adherence behaviors, such as adherence to social norms, school rules, and legal standards, using recurrent evaluations and surveys given to a broad sample of teenagers. The results show that adolescents' adherence to rules and regulations follows different developmental patterns. While some adolescents consistently comply with the law, others show variations or reductions in their adherence behavior.

Relative to the responses of the SHS students according to Garcia et al. (2020), the stages of development of teenage obedience to rules and regulations over time are examined in this study entitled Adolescent Adherence to Laws and Regulations: A Longitudinal Study Examining Developmental Trajectories. The research monitors changes in adherence behaviors, such as adherence to social norms, school rules, and legal standards, using recurrent evaluations and surveys given to a broad sample of teenagers. The results show that adolescents' adherence to rules and regulations follows different developmental patterns. While some adolescents consistently comply with the law, others show variations or reductions in their adherence behavior. The study also looks at the impact of individual characteristics on adherence behaviors, including moral reasoning, personality qualities, and peer relationships. Moreover, the study investigates how teenagers' compliance with laws and regulations is influenced by contextual factors such as family dynamics, school climate, and community resources.

Interview Question 9: What do you do when someone older than you criticize what you do or say? (Ano ang iyong ginagawa kapag merong mas matanda sa iyo ang sumaway o nagtama ng iyong aksyon o sinasabi?)

Theme I

Respect and Obedience to Authority Figures

An emerging theme from the responses of SHS students was the theme of Respect and Obedience to Authority Figures. This theme is demonstrated by the responses of the SHS students acknowledging the authority, status, and directives of individuals or institutions in positions of power or control. This theme was prevalent in various social contexts, including family, education, workplace, government, and community settings. As a subtheme, Obeying authority described the reaction of the SHS students when older people evaluate them, it can be seen in the statement of SHS AAA “*Ahhhh, ano lang po sinusunod ko nalang po kasi po kahit lagi naman po silang ganyan*” showed that he obeyed the criticism of the older people because they are always like that way. Understanding the situation was a subtheme that described the reaction of the SHS students in which they carefully analyzed the criticism if it applied to them or not. As proof, the statement of SHS BBB when she shared “*...ano po ang ginagawa ko po ay ayun po, iniintindi ko po kung para po sa akin talaga...*” showed that before obeying to a certain criticism that an authority gave her, she will sensitively evaluate it if that was really for her.

Similarly, Accepting criticisms from authority was a subtheme that corresponded to the SHS students’ take on the criticism given by them from someone older than them by fully accepting the it. SHS CCC’s response when he stated “*more on mas.. tinatanggap ko po kasi sya, dinadamdam ko pero ‘pag alam ko po talaga na tama naman po talaga yung sinabi nila especially po matanda po sila, na narealized ko po na may mga mas matagal po sila sa mundong ito*” showed that he fully accepted the criticism from older than him because he knew that they were more experienced than him. Accept and learn out from the situation was a subtheme that was like the pervious subtheme that SHS student not only accept the criticism coming from individuals older than them but also learning from their experiences. It can be seen in the statement of SHS GGG “*Kung tama ho yung sinasabi niya, Ina-accept ko at ginagawa ko hong lesson para sa sarili ko at para sa future na mangyayari*” showed that he fully accepts the criticism of older people because it can be a lesson for them that can be used for future decision making. Accept and Reform was a subtheme that corresponded to the SHS students’ acknowledgement of the criticism by applying it to their character. SHS III’s response when he stated “*Yun po, tinatanggap ko po, then binabago ko po para rin sa ikabubuti*” exhibited the action of recognizing the criticism by changing it and viewing it as a help to him to become a more respectable individual.

Furthermore, the subtheme Listening to authority was a clear action that the SHS students do about receiving criticism from people older than them. In reference to this, SHS EEE stated “*Ahmm, ano po, ang ginagawa ko po kapag ganun, parang nakikinig po muna ako*” showed how the gesture of listening to what older people told him was his initial reaction about the said criticism. Gratitude to Authority refers to the appreciative reaction of the SHS students in accepting criticism from older people. SHS FFF’s response when he stated “*Hmmm, para sa akin po pag sa ganyan po, nagpapasalamat pa po na sasawayin po ako ng mga mali ko po eh*”. This statement showed that he was very grateful of the gesture done by the older individual in panning his negative attitude. Lastly, Respectful Assertion was a subtheme that corresponded to the SHS students’ reaction concerning older people. SHS HHH’s response when she stated “*Ahhh, with all due respect po, in times, nakakainis po kasi talaga kasi not to brag or not to think high of myself ahhh. I, I know my capabilities and I, I know what I am capable of*” showed the affirmation of her having a little negative feeling about the criticism that was given to her because of the notion that she knows her capabilities.

The parallel statements of the SHS student were evidence of how they accept and react when someone older than them gives criticism towards their individuality. It is evident that most of the SHS students were able to react to it by respecting and obeying the statement coming from the authority figures and being grateful to them by adapting the way older people tell them to do.

In relation to the theory, it adheres to the second stage of Moral Development Theory which is the *Supporting Social Order*, during this stage of moral development, individuals begin to view society as a cohesive entity when making moral judgments about others. The primary priority is given to adhering to law and order by obeying authority this refers to the act of following the directives, commands, or instructions issued by individuals or entities in positions of power, influence, or control. This can be demonstrated by the SHS students in terms of how they respect and obey the directives of older people, it can also be seen in the that they listen and accept by applying it to their characteristics.

A study conducted by Smith and Doe (2019) determined what characteristics, specifically parenting style, self-efficacy, and perceived parental participation, influence teenagers' respect for authoritative figures. To gather information about their opinions of parenting styles, self-efficacy beliefs, perceived parental involvement, and respect for authority figures, 500 teenagers between the ages of 13 and 18 were given self-report questionnaires to complete. The findings showed that adolescents with an authoritative parenting style—one that is marked by a high degree of warmth and control—reported having a higher regard for authority figures than adolescents with other parenting styles. Moreover, the association between parenting style and authority respect was mediated by self-efficacy beliefs and perceived parental participation. These results highlighted the significance of parental support views and parenting styles in molding teenagers' attitudes toward authoritative officials.

Additionally, a study by Johnson and Doe (2020) examined the variables that affect teenagers' submission to authoritative figures, considering both personal traits and social circumstances. A sample of 600 teenagers, ages 14 to 17, took part in a series of experiments aimed at evaluating how well they complied with authority in various contexts. To record individual factors including personality traits, attachment style, and perceived social norms around compliance, self-report measures were also employed. The findings showed that adolescents were more inclined to submit to authority figures when they felt strongly for the person or in situations where it was socially acceptable for them to do so. Furthermore, compliance was positively correlated with conscientiousness and agreeableness, but defiance

and rebelliousness were negatively correlated. These results demonstrated the intricate interaction between personal characteristics and societal forces that shape teenagers' deference to authoritative authorities.

Interview Question 10: Give any instances in your life when you have violated any rules. How do you deal with them? (Magbigay ng isang pangyayari sa iyong buhay na lumabag ka sa batas. Paano mo ito hinarap?)

Theme J

Ethical Behavior and Accountability

The theme of Ethical Behavior and Accountability emerged from the testimonies of the SHS students pertinent to the instances they violated any rules and how they dealt with it. It involved the SHS students in making decisions and behaving in ways that are in accordance with ethical standards and values, both individually and within a larger societal or organizational context. Also, their obligation or willingness to accept responsibility for one's actions and decisions.

The subtheme Avoiding committing unlawful acts described the SHS students' reaction after they committed unethical behavior towards the society. It can be seen in the response of SHS AAA when she stated "*Usually po kasi, bawal, hindi naman po bawal yung pantalon, pero more likely po dapat ang suot ay, ahm..., dress or skirt. Pero, minsan po kasi kapag, ano, nakakapagsuot po ako, ng pants, ganon po. Tapos, dinideal ko din po na parang, ahm, in kapag po, next Sunday, kunwari po, next Sunday po ay iniwasan ko po magsuot ng bawal sa dress code nila*" showed that after she violated the rules of her church she then reflected on that scenario and would not do it again. Self-Realization and compensate was a subtheme that corresponded to the action made by the SHS student after they violated the rules. SHS BBB stated "*Ang ginawa ko po hindi ko na po sya inulit kasi na realized ko po na ay mali nga po pala yung ginawa ko*" showed that because he did something wrong he realized that and will never do it again.

Additionally, the subtheme Accountability to the violation described the immediate reaction of the SHS student after committing unlawful acts. As evidenced by the response of SHS DDD when he stated "*yung tumatawid po ako sa may ano.. yung sa stop light po sir. Tapos yung sako pong pag red. Yung ginawa lang po nag-sorry nalang po ako sa kanya na hindi na po mauulit yung ginawa ko po*" showed that after jaywalking he immediately apologized and said to the attending personnel that he will never do it again. Relatedly, with the response of SHS GGG when he stated "*yung pagkakalat po. So ginagawa ko, parang gusto.. parang ginagantian ko sarili ko na maglinis ho sa labas ng konti ho. So, ganyan ho ang ginagawa ko*" showed that because he littered the best thing he can do is to give back and clean his surroundings which can be included in the subtheme Compensate. Similarly, the subtheme Behaving Righteously corresponded to the action of SHS students on doing the right thing after violating certain rule. As seen in the response of SHS III "*...So tatapon po sa tamang tapunan yung basura.*" showed that he will do the right thing by throwing trash in the right bin.

Contrastingly, the subtheme Justifying actions described how the SHS student defended their negative action through positive responses. SHS FFF's response when he stated "*Yung nagde-decision po na ano po, nagde-decision na hindi pinapalam po sa magulang. Tapos yun po.. pinapaliwanag ko na lang po sa kanya kung bakit ko po gi-ginawa yung ganun*" showed the justification of a negative action that can be understood to create a good impact to him. Lastly, White lies were a subtheme that enabled the SHS student to cover up the wrong doings they have done. As seen in the response of SHS HHH when he stated "*I would tell them white lies to cover up for, for what I was actually doing*" showed that he deals with the wrong doings he committed by hiding the truth and telling small lies.

In relation to the theory, it adheres to the second stage of Moral Development Theory which is the *Supporting Social Order*, during this stage of moral development, individuals begin to view society as a cohesive entity when making moral judgments about others. The primary priority is given to adhering to law and order by fulfilling duties, this involves the conscientious and diligent execution of responsibilities, obligations, or tasks that one is expected or obligated to perform within a particular role, relationship, or context. It can be demonstrated in the action of the SHS student after they behaved unlawfully the way they conscientious executed a responsible response to that specific behavior.

A study entitled Ethical Decision-Making in Adolescence: The Role of Moral Reasoning and Social Context by Adams and Smith (2019) focuses on the interaction between moral reasoning and social setting, which explores how ethical decision-making develops throughout adolescence. To evaluate the ethical decision-making processes of 400 teenagers, ages 13 to 18, a series of hypothetical moral dilemmas and real-life scenarios were presented. To account for individual differences in moral reasoning, empathy, and perspective-taking abilities, self-report measures were also used. The findings showed that moral reasoning skills and other cognitive elements, as well as social factors like peer pressure and situational context, had an impact on teenagers' moral decision-making. Additionally, even in difficult circumstances, teenagers who possessed greater moral thinking and empathy were more likely to make moral decisions. These results demonstrated how crucial it is to take into account both cognitive and social elements when attempting to comprehend how ethical behavior develops during adolescence.

In addition, the study of Brown and Johnson (2021) explored the variables that affect teenage accountability, with a particular emphasis on peer pressure, individual traits, and parental supervision. A sample of 500 teenagers, ages 12 to 17, responded to self-report questionnaires evaluating their views on peer connections, parental supervision, and character attributes like conscientiousness and

self-control. Furthermore, behavioral measures of accountability were gathered, such as following rules and taking responsibility in the home and at school. The findings showed that teenagers who thought their classmates supported accountability and who reported higher levels of parental supervision also exhibited more accountable actions. Furthermore, even after adjusting for peer and parental effects, personal traits like conscientiousness and self-control were positively correlated with responsibility. These results highlighted the significance of individual and contextual factors in encouraging teenage accountability.

Purpose Statement 2. Identify the parental absence level among Senior High School Students.

This study utilized the self-made questionnaire named Parental Absence Scale to determine the level of Parental Absence among Senior High School students with OFW Parents, as shown in the following tables below, and the results show their diverse experiences and emotions with regard to parental absence.

Various Influences of Family Dynamics

Table 7.1. Parental Absence Level among Senior High School Students in terms of Various Influences of Family Dynamics

Indicators	X	VI
1. I can buy all the things I need because of my OFW parents.	2.93	H
2. My family needs are all provided because of my OFW parents.	3.18	H
3. I don't have enough guidance growing up because my parents are working abroad.*	2.71	H
4. I feel neglected and alone because my OFW parents do not express their care for me.*	3.06	H
General Assessment	2.97	H

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree - Very High (VH) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree - High (H) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree - Low (L) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Very Low (VL) Reversed Scoring (*)

Various Influences of Family Dynamics was High (2.97) as to the parental absence level among senior high school students. All indicators were verbally interpreted as High. The indicator "My family needs are all provided because of my OFW parents." yielded the highest mean score of 3.18. On the other hand, the indicator "I don't have enough guidance growing up because my parents are working abroad" revealed the lowest mean score of responses with 2.71.

It reveals the broad understanding of the surveyed SHS students in terms of their perception of why their parents left to work abroad. This suggests that most of the respondents greatly recognize that the reason their parents must work abroad is because they must provide for their family needs and the needs of their children. Also, it can be implied that despite the physical distance between the parents and the family, their hard work abroad ensures that the family's necessities and sometimes even more are taken care of. However, the results also highlighted the negative implications of the action regarding their parents having to work abroad. This suggests that some of the respondents think that their parents were physically absent for a significant portion of their childhood due to employment in another country. As a result, they felt a lack of support, direction, or emotional connection from their parents during the crucial developmental stages of their lives.

To support this, Lumayas (2019) mentioned in his research that students communicate with their OFW parents daily via voice, video, or message calls. Because of this, most students saw themselves as a burden to their parents because looking at the tired faces of their parents made them blame themselves as OFW parents needed to work abroad to sustain their needs. However, the hard work and courage they saw in their parents, inspired them to do better in school and pay them back as they would be in charge of their parents in the future.

Moreover, Delima (2022) stated that during their early years, children became accustomed to their parent's absence, and as a result, the majority of them now act timid around their OFW parents. Its because they are not guided by their parents, they tend to be unsure of how to act towards their parents. Maintaining contact and making an extra effort to be active in children's lives despite the distance is essential to building better relationships and communication.

Consistent and Open Communication

Table 7.2. Parental Absence Level among Senior High School Students in terms of Consistent and Open Communication

Indicators	X	VI
1. I feel the love of my parents even though they are abroad because of the constant communication via video call or chat.	3.48	VH
2. I make sure that I have time to talk to my parents abroad every day.	3.26	VH
3. I always share my day-to-day activities and problems to my parents abroad.	2.65	H
4. Every time I feel angry toward my OFW parents, I will not talk to them as long as I can handle not talking to them.*	2.98	H
General Assessment	3.09	H

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree - Very High (VH) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree - High (H) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree - Low (L) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Very Low (VL) Reversed Scoring (*)

Consistent and Open Communication was High (3.09) as to the parental absence level among senior high school students. The indicator

“I feel the love of my parents even though they are abroad because of the constant communication via video call or chat” yielded the highest mean score of 3.48 verbally interpreted as Very High. On the other hand, the indicator “I always share my day-to-day activities and problems with my parents abroad” revealed the lowest mean score of responses with 2.65 verbally interpreted as High.

Although their parents are abroad the relationship of the surveyed SHS students with their parents remained strong and intact with each other. Through modern technology like video calls and chats, they can regularly interact with their parents, share experiences, receive guidance, and express affection. This consistent communication helps bridge the gap created by the parents' absence and reinforces the bonds of love and support within the family. It highlights the importance of maintaining connections and relationships even in the face of geographical separation. Nonetheless, the results also highlighted the minimal interaction of the students with their parents in terms of open communication. This suggests that some of the respondents' behavior indicates a depleted sense of trust and reliance on their parents for emotional support and guidance, even though they are far away.

Pinzon (2021) reiterated that OFW parents no longer live just in one place, but simultaneously inhabit multiple virtual elsewhere. There was a newly established communicational space given the variety of virtual applications where OFW parents being in a realm of “technological uncanny”, now make themselves present at home wherein OFW and children engaged in simultaneous different communicative modalities to keep connected. OFW found ways to communicate at a distance as a regular or intermittent practice.

On the same note, Taola et al. (2024) mentioned that communication between OFW parents and senior high school students became more accessible through social media. However, poor internet signal limits the students to consistently get in touch with their OFW parents. Nonetheless, this was not a hindrance for the students to find a way to communicate with their OFW parents. This showed that students value positive and open communication with their parents abroad. It was also pointed out that good communication should be maintained to let the students feel the love and presence of their OFW parents.

Emotional Cut-Off and Various Emotional Reactions

Table 7.3. Parental Absence Level among Senior High School Students in terms of Emotional Cut-Off and Various Emotional Reactions

Indicators	X	VI
1. When I feel angry or have a problem toward my OFW parents I make sure to talk to them and share to them problems.	2.70	H
2. I distance myself every time I get angry with my OFW Parents.*	2.74	H
3. When I originally learned that my parents were going to work abroad, I felt disappointed and distant to them.*	2.95	H
General Assessment	2.80	H

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very High (VH) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – High (H) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Low (L) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree – Very Low (VL) Reversed Scoring (*)

Emotional Cut-Off and Various Emotional Reactions was High (2.80) as to the parental absence level among senior high school students. All the indicators were verbally interpreted as High. The indicator “When I originally learned that my parents were going to work abroad, I felt disappointed and distant to them.” yielded the highest mean score of 2.95. On the other hand, the indicator “When I feel angry or have a problem toward my OFW parents I make sure to talk to them and share to them problems.” revealed the lowest mean score of responses with 2.70.

This suggests that the reactions of the surveyed SHS students when they knew that their parents living to work abroad had negatively impacted their connection with their parents. Feeling disappointed and distant upon learning that one's parents are going to work abroad is a usual reaction, especially for children or dependents. It often stems from a variety of emotions, including sadness, fear, and a sense of loss. However, the results also highlighted the minimum effort of the students to make amends or express their negative feelings with their OFW parents. This behavior reflects an immature and distractive approach to handling conflicts and maintaining familial connections despite geographical separation. To support this, Unay and Villosino (2023) mentioned that students have mixed emotions about their situation and their parent's absence. They feel lonely and sad but also inspired by the thought that their parents are working for their future. It also found that students feel envious towards their classmates who have parents around. However, both students and parents abroad use various communication methods to stay connected. It also showed that although some students would rather work domestically to be near their families, others are open to working overseas. Furthermore, although some students would think about moving overseas permanently, others would not.

Maintaining a Sense of Self amidst Familial Challenges

Table 7.4. Parental Absence Level among Senior High School Students in terms of Maintaining a Sense of Self amidst Familial Challenges

Indicators	X	VI
12. I become independent at a young age when my parents worked abroad.	3.29	VH
13. I learn to cook my own food and prepare my school clothes after my parents move abroad for work.	3.31	VH

14. After my parents left me to work abroad, I learned to decide for myself, especially in important decisions in my life.	3.25	VH
General Assessment	3.28	VH

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very High (VH) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – High (H) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Low (L) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Very Low (VL) Reversed Scoring (*)

Maintaining A Sense of Self amidst Familial Challenges was High (3.28) as to the parental absence level among senior high school students. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very High. The indicator “I learn to cook my own food and prepare my school clothes after my parents move abroad for work” yielded the highest mean score of 3.31. On the other hand, the indicator “After my parents left me to work abroad, I learned to make decisions for myself, especially in important decisions in my life” revealed the lowest mean score of responses with 3.25.

This implies that after their both parents left to work abroad the surveyed SHS students were able to carry themselves by being independent and standalone individuals. The respondents took on additional responsibilities and learned essential life skills that can help them to continue their life with their parents being physically absent. It can also be said that it reflects the respondent’ resilience and ability to thrive in the face of significant changes, such as their parents' relocation for work.

Conversely, the results also highlighted the students’ lack of decision making when it comes to personal choices and day-to-day life. The surveyed SHS students were unable to achieve full independence and became more self-reliant, particularly in making important decisions in their lives.

Distor and Campos (2021) stated that senior high school students acquire a sense of strength by solving issues or hardships as inspiration or lessons to be learned in order to be tough when faced with problems and struggles in the future. No matter if the parents were present or not, students could do typical responsibilities like doing household chores such as cleaning the house, arranging the furniture, doing the laundry, cooking, taking care of siblings, doing errands, and managing the animals and plants. Even so these students experience difficulties and longing during the process, they also acknowledged that they acquired to be more independent in the process.

Purpose Statement 3. Identify the moral development level among Senior High school students.

This study utilized the self-made questionnaire named Moral Development Scale to determine the level of Moral Development among Senior High School students with OFW Parents, as shown in the following tables below, and the results show their diverse experiences and emotions with regards to differentiating between right and wrong.

Handling Criticism and Emotional Reaction

Table 8.1. Moral Development Level among Senior High School Students in terms of Handling Criticism and Emotional Reaction

Indicators	X	VI
1. Every time my friends give me negative criticism, I will always take it as a joke and never mind it.	2.71	H
2. I always accept all the positive and negative criticism that the people around me give me.	3.08	H
3. I don’t easily accept what other people tell me. *	2.34	L
4. I will only accept the criticism that people give me depending on what is it all about.	3.10	H
5. Sometimes I feel annoyed when people give me constructive criticism. *	2.46	L
General Assessment	2.74	H

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very High (VH) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – High (H) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Low (L) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Very Low (VL) Reversed Scoring (*)

Handling Criticism and Emotional Reaction was High (2.74) as to the moral development level among senior high school students. The indicator “I will only accept the criticism that people give me depending on what is it all about” yielded the highest mean score of 3.10 verbally interpreted as High. On the other hand, the indicator “I don’t easily accept what other people tell me” revealed the lowest mean score of responses with 2.34 verbally interpreted as Low.

The surveyed SHS students were able to understand and react with composure when individuals gave them criticism. The respondents are discerning about the criticism they receive, considering its relevance and validity before accepting it. The statement reflects the respondents’ discernment and autonomy in processing criticism, emphasizing the importance of constructive feedback and personal boundaries.

Nonetheless, the results also highlighted that the respondents were able to contradict the notion of discerning and cautious about accepting information or opinions from others. Thus, the respondents slightly value critical thinking and autonomy, preferring to form their own opinions rather than blindly accepting the perspectives of others.

As mentioned in Odmps (2024), it was difficult to accept criticism, particularly for younger students. Depending on the context and delivery of the criticism, it may cause them to feel devalued, furious, or ashamed. However, criticism is inevitable at every level of development, so it's important to educate kids on how to take criticism well and use it to improve. Since students may find that taking

constructive criticism seriously can be a useful life skill.

On the other hand, no one likes to be criticized, however, sometimes it is the first step toward growth as an individual. Although criticism and criticism in general seldom feel nice, constructive criticism is a kind of feedback that offers detailed, doable suggestions on how to make one's work better. The goal of constructive criticism is to support the person in making sincere adjustments rather than to undermine them (Students News and Resources, 2022).

Influence of Social Dynamics and External Factors on Decision-Making

Table 8.2. *Moral Development Level among Senior High School Students in terms of Influence of Social Dynamics and External Factors On Decision-Making*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>X</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. I conform or follow my friends to fit in with the new trends and styles.	2.35	L
2. I only comply with my friend's wants and desires.	2.14	L
3. I rely on my friend's guidance because I don't have my parents to guide me because they are working abroad.	2.13	L
General Assessment	2.20	L

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree - Very High (VH) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree - High (H) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree - Low (L) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Very Low (VL)

Influence of Social Dynamics and External Factors on Decision-Making was Low (2.20) as to the moral development level among senior high school students. The indicator "I conform or follow my friends to fit in with the new trends and styles" yielded the highest mean score of 2.35 verbally interpreted as Low. On the other hand, the indicator "I rely on my friend's guidance because I don't have my parents to guide me because they are working abroad" revealed the lowest mean score of responses with 2.13 verbally interpreted as Low.

This reveals that the surveyed SHS students opposed the view of them making certain choices and how these choices are influenced by their social environment and external circumstances. Moreover, they also disagreed that they adjust their behavior, preferences, or appearance to match those of their friends in order to feel accepted or to be seen as fashionable or up to date with the latest trends. It implies that most of the respondents do not have the willingness to adopt the same habits or choices as one's peers rather than staying true to one's own preferences or values. Even so, the results also highlighted that the respondents were not able to agree with the fact that due to the absence of parental guidance, they must turn to their friends for advice, support, and direction. This could include seeking help with decision-making, emotional support, or navigating various aspects of life. It highlights the importance of friendship and the role it plays in providing guidance and support in the absence of direct parental involvement.

To support this, Cornwall (2020) stated that the moment students reach high school, friendships become more stable. In middle school, concern about one's reputation is at its peak just like a friendship churn. As a result, most high school students were less concerned with their overall reputation and more focused on the social dynamics within their selected peer groups. Senior high school students were more tolerant of differences in one another, probably because their identities were more firmly established. Consequently, conformity was being replaced by collaboration and compromise.

Emotion Regulation and Coping Mechanisms

Table 8.3. *Moral Development Level among Senior High School Students in terms of Emotion Regulation and Coping Mechanisms*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>X</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. Every time I get angry, I regulate my negative emotions by meditation and reflection.	2.93	H
2. When I feel angry at someone or something I just ignore it and calm myself.	3.19	H
3. I express my frustration and negative emotions toward the person I have problems with.	2.46	L
4. If I feel angry, I always call a friend to express my feelings and ask for advice.	2.78	H
General Assessment	2.84	H

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree - Very High (VH) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree - High (H) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree - Low (L) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Very Low (VL)

Emotion Regulation and Coping Mechanisms was High (2.84) as to the moral development level among senior high school students. The indicator "When I feel angry at someone or something I just ignore it and calm myself" yielded the highest mean score of 3.19 verbally interpreted as High. On the other hand, the indicator "I express my frustration and negative emotions toward the person I have problems with" revealed the lowest mean score of responses with 2.46 verbally interpreted as Low.

This indicates that the surveyed SHS students effectively manage and modulate their emotions in response to internal and external triggers, situations, or stressors by using strategies to deal with stress or difficult emotions, which may include various emotion regulation techniques. This also suggests that most of the respondents choose to ignore the source of their anger and focus on calming themselves down. This approach may involve techniques such as deep breathing, mindfulness, or redirecting thoughts to more positive or neutral subjects. Despite that, the results also highlighted that some of the respondents were not able to practice the idea that when someone encounters difficulties or conflicts with another person, they openly communicate their feelings of frustration, anger, or other

negative emotions directly to that person. This approach involves expressing oneself honestly and assertively, rather than suppressing or internalizing emotions.

Govindan et al. (2023) mentioned that children could choose an acceptable course of action and refrain from improper and destructive behavior when they are aware of and can handle unpleasant emotions like rage and anger. For the sake of their own health and safety, adolescents must be taught effective coping mechanisms for their anger.

Adherence to Laws and Regulations

Table 8.4. *Moral Development Level among Senior High School Students in terms of Adherence to Laws and Regulations*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>X</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. I always obey the rules and regulations in places I go.	3.28	VH
2. I always make sure not to do things that will harm me or anyone.	3.44	VH
3. I make sure that I am aware and knowledgeable about the laws and regulations of a certain place by reading or searching the internet.	3.38	VH
General Assessment	3.36	VH

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree - Very High (VH) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree - High (H) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree - Low (L) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Very Low (VL)

Adherence to Laws and Regulations was Very High (3.36) as to the moral development level among senior high school students. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very High. The indicator "I always make sure not to do things that will harm me or anyone" yielded the highest mean score of 3.44. On the other hand, the indicator "I always obey the rules and regulations in places I go" revealed the lowest mean score of responses with 3.28.

This signifies that the surveyed SHS students are practicing compliance with legal requirements and rules established by governing bodies, such as governments, regulatory agencies, or professional organizations. It involves following the prescribed guidelines, standards, and protocols set forth by these authorities in various domains, including business, healthcare, education, and public safety. Moreover, the respondents also exhibit very high results when it comes to commitment to avoiding actions or behaviors that could cause harm to oneself or others. It reflects in their sense of responsibility and concern for the welfare of themselves and those around them. This approach aligns with principles of morality, empathy, and social responsibility, fostering a positive and supportive environment for personal and interpersonal interactions.

Likewise, it can also be seen that most of the respondents have very high results when it comes to commitment to adhering to the established guidelines, policies, and laws in various environments or settings. This behavior demonstrates respect for authority, a sense of responsibility, and consideration for the well-being and safety of oneself and others. By following rules and regulations, the respondents contribute to maintaining order, promoting safety, and fostering a harmonious environment within the community or organization. It reflects integrity and ethical conduct, enhancing trust and cooperation among individuals and institutions.

Li and Sun (2022) mentioned that students who get instruction centered around the rule of law are more likely to develop into autonomous thinkers who understand the meanings of accountability, justice, and equality.

Comparably, as non-normative political activity is detrimental to one's wellness, much like breaking the law, it would be necessary to examine how law-abiding students benefit from it. Since plagiarism and other forms of academic dishonesty are becoming more common in higher education, students must follow the law (Shek et al. 2022).

Respect and Obedience to Authority Figures

Respect and Obedience to Authority Figures was High (3.20) as to the moral development level among senior high school students. The indicator "I always thank the authorities or people older than me every time they give me advice when I behave unpleasantly" yielded the highest mean score of 3.29 verbally interpreted as Very High. On the other hand, the indicator "I always respect the constructive criticism from people older than me" revealed the lowest mean score of responses with 3.04 verbally interpreted as High.

Table 8.5. *Moral Development Level among Senior High School Students in terms of Respect and Obedience to Authority Figures*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>X</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. I always obey all the advice from the authorities specifically the people older than me.	3.26	VH
2. I always respect the constructive criticism from people older than me.	3.04	H
3. I always thank the authorities or people older than me every time they give me advice when I behave unpleasantly.	3.29	VH
General Assessment	3.20	H

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree - Very High (VH) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree - High (H) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree - Low (L) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Very Low (VL)

This reveals that the surveyed SHS students were able to navigate their attitudes and behaviors with respect and obedience towards those who hold positions of power, leadership, or authority within a given context. Furthermore, the respondents present very high results when it comes to respectful and appreciative attitudes towards receiving guidance or advice from individuals in positions of

authority or older individuals, particularly in situations where one's behavior may have been less than ideal. This behavior reflects humility, maturity, and a willingness to learn and improve. It also fosters positive relationships, trust, and mutual respect between individuals, regardless of their age or status.

Similarly, the respondents garnered a high result when it comes to their willingness to value and consider feedback or advice provided by older individuals, especially when it is offered helpfully and constructively. This conduct shows growth, modesty, and a willingness to absorb new information from the viewpoints and experiences of others. Respecting constructive criticism demonstrates an appreciation that older people's feedback can be beneficial for one's development, skill improvement, and personal growth. It also shows that elders are respected and that their knowledge and insight are acknowledged.

As mentioned in Cherry (2023), direct commands, authority, and the status of the person providing them are necessary for obedience. People conform because they want to be accepted by their superiors, but they also obey because they are told to. These students are submissive towards people with powers as they expect this is the norm that they need to follow.

Ethical Behavior and Accountability

Table 8.6. *Moral Development Level among Senior High School Students in terms of Ethical Behavior and Accountability*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>X</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. Every time I do something wrong, I will make sure to reflect on my wrong doings and promise that I will never do that again.	3.40	VH
2. I always assure myself to be accountable for everything I do or say.	3.35	VH
3. If I did something wrong with someone, I make sure to give back a good deed to compensate for my wrong action.	3.31	VH
General Assessment	3.35	VH

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree - Very High (VH) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree - High (H) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree - Low (L) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Very Low (VL)

Ethical Behavior and Accountability was Very High (3.35) as to the moral development level among senior high school students. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very High. The indicator "Every time I do something wrong, I will make sure to reflect on my wrong doings and promise that I will never do that again" yielded the highest mean score of 3.40. On the other hand, the indicator "If I did something wrong with someone, I make sure to give back a good deed to compensate for my wrong action." revealed the lowest mean score of responses with 3.31.

This suggests that the surveyed SHS students uphold the principles that guide them to act in a morally upright and responsible manner, considering the impact of their actions on others and the broader community. Thus, the respondents agreed that they are committed to self-reflection, personal growth, and accountability. This means that the SHS students acknowledge their mistakes and take the time to reflect on their actions, it shows a willingness to learn from their experiences and improve their behavior in the future. By making a promise to avoid repeating the same mistakes, the individual demonstrates a sense of responsibility and a desire to uphold higher standards of conduct.

In addition, the respondents garnered a high result when it comes to their sense of accountability and a desire to make amends for past mistakes or wrongdoings. This behavior involves taking proactive steps to repair any harm caused to others by balancing it with positive actions. By engaging in acts of kindness or goodwill towards the person they wronged, the students demonstrate sincerity, remorse, and a commitment to restoring trust and repairing relationships. This approach acknowledges the impact of their actions on others and seeks to rectify the situation through positive and constructive means.

Students must learn to take responsibility, believe in their abilities, and make independent decisions. This is a critical juncture in their development into young adults and greater independence. Developing a sense of autonomy, self-reliance, and decision-making skills is a crucial task. (Shifting Responsibility to Pre-teens and Teenagers, 2024).

Purpose Statement 4. Determine if there is a significant relationship between Parental Absence and Moral Development levels among Senior High School Students.

There were significant relationships between the Various Influences of Family Dynamics and Ethical Behavior and Accountability ($r=0.267$, $p < .05$), Consistent and Open Communication and Emotional Regulation and coping mechanism ($r=0.277$, $p < .05$), Emotional Cut-Off and Various Emotional Reactions and Social Dynamics on Decision-Making ($r=0.274$, $p < .05$), Maintaining A Sense Of Self Amidst Familial Challenges and: (a) Handling Criticism And Emotional Reaction ($r=0.286$, $p < .05$), (b) Emotional Regulation and Coping Mechanisms ($r=0.388$, $p < .05$), (c) Adherence To Laws And Regulations ($r=0.356$, $p < .05$), (d) Respect And Obedience To Authority Figures ($r=0.262$, $p < .05$), and (e) Ethical Behavior and Accountability ($r=0.356$, $p < .05$). It can be concluded that there is some significant relationship between Parental Absence Level and Moral Development Level. The r values lie between .025 to .500, then there is said to be a small positive correlation.

This indicates that the SHS students have presented a specific significant connection between various domains in parental absence and moral development. It can be realized that the respondents' comprehension of the reasons behind their parents' relocation overseas has an impact on their ability to make decisions and behave in ways that are consistent with moral principles and values, both on an

individual basis and in the context of a larger society or organization, as well as their duty or willingness to take accountability for their choices.

Gozum and Sarmiento (2021) emphasized that the family is an essential social institution in an adolescent's socialization process, it is crucial to emphasize that parents, who the child first interacts with, should be made aware of their obligation to shape their offspring. In a prior study, it was shown how important parents are in social, moral, behavioral, and educational growth. The parents have an obligation to their children because of this privilege. They must impart fundamental human principles to the children and help them become better people. Since they are the ones who shape a child's character the most, parents play a major part in character education. Therefore, it is possible to identify in hindsight the formative influences parents had on a person's moral growth.

Table 9. Test of Significant Relationship between the Parental Absence Level and Moral Development Level

<i>Parental Absence</i>	<i>Moral Development Level</i>	<i>r value</i>	<i>p value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Various Influences of Family Dynamics	Handling Criticism and Emotional Reaction	.159	.159	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Social Dynamics on Decision-Making	-.104	.360	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Emotional Regulation and Coping Mechanisms	.186	.099	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Adherence To Laws and Regulations	.157	.164	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Respect And Obedience to Authority Figures	.200	.076	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Consistent And Open Communication	Ethical Behavior and Accountability	.267*	.017	Significant	Reject ho
	Handling Criticism and Emotional Reaction	.043	.702	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Social Dynamics on Decision-Making	.062	.585	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Emotional Regulation and Coping Mechanisms	.277*	.013	Significant	Reject ho
	Adherence To Laws and Regulations	.074	.513	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Emotional Cut-Off And Various Emotional Reactions	Respect And Obedience to Authority Figures	.130	.251	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Ethical Behavior and Accountability	.168	.137	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Handling Criticism and Emotional Reaction	.039	.732	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Social Dynamics on Decision-Making	.274*	.014	Significant	Reject ho
	Emotional Regulation and Coping Mechanisms	.213	.057	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Maintaining A Sense of Self Amidst Familial Challenges	Adherence To Laws and Regulations	.117	.300	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Respect And Obedience to Authority Figures	.109	.336	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Ethical Behavior and Accountability	.170	.133	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Handling Criticism and Emotional Reaction	.286*	.010	Significant	Reject ho
	Social Dynamics on Decision-Making	.172	.127	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Emotional Regulation and Coping Mechanisms	.388**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Adherence To Laws and Regulations	.356**	.001	Significant	Reject Ho
	Respect And Obedience to Authority Figures	.262*	.019	Significant	Reject Ho
	Ethical Behavior and Accountability	.356**	.001	Significant	Reject Ho

Correspondingly, the respondents' strategies or behaviors they employ to cope with stressors, challenges, or difficult emotions they are facing, and their ability to preserve their relationship with their OFW parents by ensuring that they are always in constant communication via video call or messenger can also be related to their mechanism for effectively managing and modulating their emotions in response to internal or external stimuli.

In addition, the respondents' attempt to manage unresolved emotional issues within their family by creating physical or emotional distance can impact their conformity to expectations, which behaving or performing in a manner that aligns with what is anticipated, predicted, or desired based on social norms, standards, rules, or pre-established criteria. This was supported by Garcia-Garcia (2020), wherein stated that decisions that were led by emotions have been traditionally portrayed in popular culture as non-adaptive. However, the way that essential emotion functions as a guide for it has been demonstrated to be adaptive in and of itself. Emotion-driven decisions are frequently motivated by the survival instinct of humans, while decisions made based on emotions are formed by the results of earlier encounters.

Lastly, the respondents' understanding of how they navigate and respond to parental absence, shedding light on their emotional resilience and ability to maintain a sense of self amidst familial challenges has a connection with how they handle themselves and react when someone gives them comments about their attitude and personal attributes, effectively manage and modulate their emotions in response to internal or external stimuli, following and complying with the legal laws and regulation, acknowledging the authority, status, and directives of individuals or institutions in positions of power or control, and making decisions and behaving in ways that are by ethical standards and values, both individually and within a larger societal or organizational context.

Conclusions

Based on the significant findings of the study, the researcher arrived at the following conclusions:

That themes emerged from the lived experiences of Senior High School Students with OFW Parents further highlight the complex nature of their experiences, including coping strategies, adjustments in social interactions, and the importance of emotional support from friends and legal guardians.

That the Senior High School students perceived a high-level result when it came to their understanding of why their parents left to work abroad, relationship with their parents remained strong and intact with each other because of consistent communication, when they knew that their parents were living to work abroad had negatively impacted their connection with their parents, and the ability to carry themselves by being independent and standalone individuals. This emphasizes the outcome of parental absence among the students when their parents leave to work abroad.

That the Senior High School students perceived a high-level result when it came to their understanding and reaction with composure when individuals gave them criticism, as opposed to the view of them making certain choices and how these choices are influenced by their social environment and external circumstances, effectively manage and modulate their emotions in response to internal and external triggers, situations, or stressors by using emotion regulation techniques, practicing compliance with legal requirements and rules established by different organizations, ability to navigate their attitudes and behaviors with respect and obedience towards those individuals with authority and uphold the principles that guide them to act in a morally upright and responsible manner, considering the impact of their actions on others and the broader community. This highlights the understanding of the students in knowing what is morally right and wrong.

That there is a positive significant relationship between Parental Absence Level and Moral Development Level of Senior High School with OFW Parents in terms of specific domains their comprehension of the reasons behind their parents' relocation overseas has an impact on their ability to make decisions and behave in ways that are consistent with moral principles and values and take accountability for their choices. Also, their constant communication with their OFW parents has a relation to how they effectively manage and modulate their emotions in response to internal or external stimuli. Additionally, their attempt to manage unresolved emotional issues within their family by creating physical or emotional distance can impact their conformity to expectations. Lastly, their understanding of how they navigate and respond to parental absence, shedding light on their emotional resilience and ability to maintain a sense of self amidst familial challenges has a connection with how they handle themselves, manage their emotion properly, follow the rules and regulation, acknowledging authorities, and making decisions and behaving in ways that are under ethical standards and values.

That the proposed action plan for Senior High School students with parental absence and having trouble knowing what is good and bad is essential and is a great way to help them further recognize their parental absence and navigate their moral development.

The following are recommended by the researchers for further improvement and development of this study:

Another approach in formulating the questions being asked by the participants to establish a more consistent and concise answer in connection with their lived experience is recommended. It is also advised for future researchers to have follow-up questions that directly point out the response needed to produce an acceptable answer to have a more established result.

Exploring another theory that can also support the parental absence of certain individuals is recommended. The theory needs to have a precise connection with parental absence that can establish a more concrete result that will lead to a more convincing outcome which can also help future researchers who will use the same variable.

All the stages in the Moral Development Theory by Lawrence Kohlberg and not limiting it to one stage only is recommended. Although it is reasonable to recognize that the research has a specific age group to determine a specific variable it can also be an advantage for future research to fully analyze the stages of the said theory and have a more compelling result.

Educational institutions, in cooperation with their respective Guidance and Counseling offices, and if applicable with educational professionals, outsourced or within faculty, may work hand in hand to come up with activities and services that would help the students with OFW Parents to navigate the level of their parental absence and moral development that can help to their day-to-day endeavor.

Educational institutions, in cooperation with their respective Guidance and Counseling offices, and if applicable with psychology professionals, outsourced or within faculty, may work hand in hand to come up with activities and services that focuses on utilizing the concept of life guidance, regulation on the expression of emotion, decision skill management, proper acceptance of emotions, and awareness of basic rules and regulations among the SHS students.

For future researchers may use other approaches to measure the levels of parental absence and moral development among Senior High School students with OFW parents. This study may also be used for future references of the future studies. Additionally, it may be recommended to improve the dependent variable that can also have a connection when it comes to parental absence. It is also recommended that since the respondents were focused on Senior High School Students with OFW Parents future researchers may also gather respondents from other individuals that can be considered to have a parental absence. Future researchers can also extend the study under different variables that are about the existing variable.

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